

Deliverable D3.2 – WP3. Report on HIKR Design

EURAKNOS

*Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs towards a European
Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System*

TASK 3.2: DESIGN OF A HIKR

Summary

The overall aim of EURAKNOS is to connect all the materials, knowledge and platforms of existing TNs in one electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP) to map the stored knowledge within each network, and to design a common data system to make this knowledge better accessible, findable, interoperable and reusable for the agricultural innovation community in Europe. Deliverable 3.2 describes the different steps and conclusions made in order to define the design and tools (software, data formats) to be used for a HIKR in perspective of construction of the prototype of the common e-Knowledge Platform (e-KRP), and communication and dissemination perspectives to the end user. In order to achieve this goal a workshop with experts was held on different topics related to creating a data model and constructing the EURAKNOS repository. This has allowed us to propose the EURAKNOS data model and proceed to an initial outline of the technological framework (including data storage, metadata storage, and search engine). To conclude, a strategy to move from the HIKR to the e-KRP is presented including recommendations on how to attain a user-friendly and accessible digital platform.

Deliverable Number	Work Package
3.2	WP3
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Planned Delivery Date	Actual Delivery Date
30/04/2020	30/04/2020

Type of Deliverable	R	Document, report (excluding periodic and final reports)	X
	DEC	Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos	
	E	Ethics	

Dissemination Level	PU	Public	X
	CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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List of abbreviations

API: Application Programming Interface
BSD: Berkeley Software Distribution
CMS: Content Management System
EIP-AGRI: European Innovation Partnership for Agriculture
e-KRP: electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform
EUFRA: European Forum for Agricultural and Rural Advisory Services
EURAKNOS: Connecting Thematic Networks as Knowledge Reservoirs: towards a European Agricultural Knowledge Innovation Open Source System
EUREKA: European Knowledge Repository for Best Agricultural Practices
FAIR: Findable Accessible Interoperable and Reusable
HIKR: High Impact Knowledge Reservoir
JSON: JavaScript Object Notation
KIP: Knowledge Innovation Panel

KR: Knowledge Reservoir
MA: Multi-Actor
MS: Member State
MVP: Minimum Viable Product
PSKW: Proefstation voor de Groenteteelt Sint-Katelijne-Waver
RDF: Resource Description Framework
SQL: Structured Query Language
TN: Thematic Network
UML: Unified Modelling Language
URL: Uniform Resource Locator
WG: Working Group
WHO: World Health Organisation
WP: Work Package
XML: Extensible Markup Language

1. Introduction

A common challenge for Thematic Networks (TNs) is the sustainability of the knowledge collected after the funding period of the project. Given the needs for financial resources to store TN outputs, ensure easy access, and regular updates in the long term to the technical infrastructure, a substantial part of the outputs of TNs is at risk of becoming easily outdated or unavailable to relevant end users such as advisory services, farmers and foresters.

Moreover, TNs are very diverse in their themes and scope, and produce a wide variety of dissemination material, making it hard for the end-users to maintain a clear overview of the knowledge available that could provide potential solutions to the problems they seek guidance for. Additionally, given that information is scattered over a multitude of platforms and websites, end-users make use of popular search engines such as Google, Bing or Ecosia in order to find the knowledge they need. However, the provided results are not always accessible (e.g., paywall), available in the user's native language, easily applicable to their context, or trustworthy.

Finally, creating a digital knowledge reservoir can be a daunting challenge for TNs. The end product may be a platform that indeed makes knowledge available, but lacks a consistent design, and/or violates general principles of usability towards end-users (e.g., a platform that enables no easy access to data). These challenges core to Task 3.2: Design of a HIKR (High-Impact Knowledge Reservoir).

The main goal of Task 3.2 is to identify in a participatory way the best design and format for a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) focussing on farmers, foresters & advisors. Task 3.2 has carried out activities to define the design as a common format and tools (software, data formats) to be used for a HIKR in perspective of construction of the prototype of the common e-Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP) (WP4), and communication and dissemination perspectives to the end-user.

Within this context, the aim of this document is to frame the concept of the High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR), present and describe the EURAKNOS data model (core to the design of the HIKR), based on the methodology presented next, illustrate a number of considerations regarding the types of the data (and formats of the content and information conveyed) needed to be stored into the HIKR, as well as present a future vision for the EURAKNOS electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP) through the HIKR.

2. Methodology

Task 3.2 builds upon the results of the work implemented in Work Package 2 (Deliverables 2.1 and 2.2) and Work Package 3 (Deliverable 3.1). Insights available from the report of Deliverable 4.1 have been also useful for the design of the EURAKNOS data model.

To begin with, preliminary work was performed on the definition of the concept of Thematic Networks and the identification of key terms & the relations between them. This early work was the foundation for the creation of the draft version of a potential EURAKNOS data model based on the methodology of Noy and McGuiness (2001).

Subsequently, a 2-day workshop (WP3) was organised in Paris from the 12th to the 13th December 2019. The input for this workshop came from exercises and discussions during the Athens consortium meeting (held in June 2019; WP1), as well as the Budapest workshop (reported in Deliverable 2.5), and aimed at making decisions in regard to the scope of the HIKR, the EURAKNOS data model, the features required, and the future vision of the HIKR for TNs and potential end users.

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To further elaborate on the outcomes of the working group, Task 3.2 held weekly sessions with a team of 10 technical experts, suggested by the KIP (Knowledge Innovation Panel), as well as members of the EURAKNOS consortium having a technical background and experience in complex IT projects, to discuss the issues of concern for the data model creation and technology choices. Based on these discussions, a technology framework has been proposed and a phasing of the EURAKNOS platform, beyond the EURAKNOS project, has been suggested.

Furthermore, a survey to advisors was conducted during the EUFAS meeting¹ in Athens. The survey took place on the 25th of February 2020 and was implemented by administering questionnaires to a sample of 32 advisors. Next, the state-of-the-art of accessibility and usability guidelines was researched as input for the prototype and future vision which will be developed in WP 4.

The methodology employed in Task 3.2 is shown with the help of the diagram in Figure 1 below. The insights, conclusions, and recommendations are compiled in this deliverable report.

Figure 1: Overview of the methodology adopted in Task 3.2

¹ <http://www.eufas.eu/index.php/activities/archive/142-eufas-annual-assembly-2020>

3. Design WG Meeting

3.1 Working Group objective

The DoA states that "The design WG will be set up to identify and file recommendations for best methodologies and practices to design a HIKR. Design WG members (ca. 10) will be selected from the KIP. The findings will be synthesized in a report discussed and validated by all the partners involved in the work package, describing the methodologies and practices to design a HIKR."

3.2 Working Group participants

The workshop participants were suggested by the KIP (Knowledge Innovation Panel) and EURAKNOS consortium. During this phase in the project, Task 3.2 is mostly focusing on solving the technical challenges in setting up a High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR).

For this reason, only people with a highly technical background and experience in complex IT projects were invited to the working group. An invitation to the workshop was sent to a list of 30 experts.

The workshop was attended by a total number of twelve (12) experts coming from diverse backgrounds (2 research, 2 IT project management, 6 software and data engineering, 2 digital design) and countries (Belgium, Denmark, France, Greece, Hungary, The Netherlands).

3.3 Working Group content & outcome

The goal of the WG3.2 workshop (i.e. the workshop related to the activities involved in the design of the HIKR), which took place in the EURAKNOS Paris meeting, was to present the initial design-related considerations to the guest participants and get involved in a fruitful brainstorming and discussion with the aim to receive feedback and make decisions about a number of design- and development-related issues.

The overarching research questions on which the WG meeting focused were the following:

- How can data available from TNs be collected and integrated into a HIKR?
- In which ways could the EURAKNOS data model serve as a basis for future TNs?

The above research questions were further analysed in a number of topics that were used as a guide for the discussion implemented in the context of the workshop:

1. Technical issues that need to be tackled.
2. Scope and expectations from WG3.2 working group.
3. EURAKNOS data model: Can it adequately and efficiently represent the structure of data? Do we need to further elaborate and extend upon it?
4. Need to comply with Open data standards and FAIR data principles.
5. Data integration.
6. Search engine technologies to consider.
7. HIKR interoperability and implications for backend design.
8. End-user types, content needs and implications for search patterns.
9. Learning from TN best practices.

For each of the topics (topics 1 to 5 were those that were more extensively addressed), an introduction and initial, design-related considerations were presented to the group of technical experts. Topic per topic feedback was gathered from every participant in the working group. The feedback received from the presentation of a draft version² of the EURAKNOS data model³ indicated that the data structure proposed is adequate for providing a solution to the problem at hand (i.e. the adequate and efficient storage of the range of outputs available by the KR of TNs).

A significant contribution of the workshop related also to the recommendations received with regard to the technologies that should be considered for developing the HIKR⁴ (and, thus, the e-KRP⁵). More specifically, one of the topics addressed in the WG3.2 workshop related to the need to “*comply with Open data standards and FAIR data principles*” and the implications for the selection of technologies. The solution that had been initially considered for the e-KRP, and presented to the workshop, was based on a stack of technologies comprising a popular NoSQL⁶ database system (i.e. MongoDB) and a search engine system built on top of it (based on either Solr or Elasticsearch). According to the feedback received, such a solution could indeed fit the purpose of EURAKNOS and work, but, given the fact that it is a custom-made, in-house solution, there could be difficulties in its maintenance especially after the end of the project. It was suggested that attention should be paid to existing frameworks for creating open repositories able to not only deliver content, but also to manage and curate it. Such solutions allow to easily comply with the Open data standards and FAIR principles, which is a requisite for the EURAKNOS HIKR and e-KRP.

In this context, DSpace has been proposed as a solution interesting to investigate and adopt, given its rich set of features, the vibrant community built around it and the number of projects that have been built on it. Based on the feedback received: (i) the conceptual design process (which is documented in the following chapters) has been continued and resulted in the data model presented in this document; and (ii) the process of the HIKR (and e-KRP) development, which is currently in progress, has been initiated.

² The final version of the EURAKNOS data model described in this document is based, in almost its entirety, in the draft version presented in the WG3.2 workshop in Paris. It has been produced as the result of fine tuning the draft version with the aim to better capture and illustrate important characteristics of the digital outputs (i.e., data objects) available by TNs. In order to keep the descriptions provided clear and understandable, the final outcome of the design process (i.e., the final version of the EURAKNOS data model) is presented.

³ A definition of the term “data model” together with an explanation of its role and need are provided in the subsection 4.2.1 (“What is a data model and why is it needed?”).

⁴ The concept of the HIKR is extensively addressed in the “Framing the concept of ‘High Impact Knowledge Reservoir’” section of the document. It is used to refer to the data repository lying at the back-end of the EURAKNOS electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform (e-KRP).

⁵ The term “e-KRP” is used to denote the EURAKNOS electronic Knowledge Reservoir Platform in its entirety including both back-end (i.e., the HIKR) and front-end components (i.e., the user interface).

⁶ According to Wikipedia (“<https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/NoSQL>”), NoSQL data stores provide data storage and retrieval mechanisms “*modeled in means other than the tabular relations used in relational databases*”.

4. Designing the EURAKNOS HIGH IMPACT KNOWLEDGE RESERVOIR

4.1 Framing the concept of “High Impact Knowledge Reservoir”

TNs are multi-actor efforts focussing on the creation, collection, and dissemination of data objects that convey agriculture- and forestry-related content and information. As Marois et al. (2019) point out, data disseminated by TNs has been assembled into fit-for-purpose collections, termed as KRs, with the aim to facilitate the community’s access to knowledge. A KR is a collection of best materials, practices, instruments, methodologies, and tools aiming to contribute to the uptake and re-use of innovative solutions for sustainable agriculture and forestry. From a technical perspective, a KR relates to the technologies and tools employed for enabling data storage and user access to content and information.

As made evident by the analysis of Marois et al. (2019), there is a number of metaphors that have been employed by the existing TNs for the needs of making agriculture-related content and information available to the end-users. These metaphors are:

- **KR as a catalogue** with an emphasis on functionalities for assisting and supporting the end-user in the search and retrieval of digital content.
- **KR as a library** with an emphasis on the classification of digital content with regard to the types of data objects available and the topics addressed.
- **KR as a practical, digital guidebook** with an emphasis on the provision of ready-to-use and easy-to-apply solutions tailored to the needs of the end-users that are targeted.
- **KR as a marketplace (for the exchange of good practices)** with an emphasis on redirecting the user to web-based information environments of interest.

The diversity in the metaphors adopted has led to various solutions for the architecture of information and structuring of the provided data, which appear to be based on custom-made conceptual designs. This diversity is explicitly stressed in one of the concluding remarks made in the report of Deliverable 2.2 (“Design of Knowledge Reservoirs within current and past Thematic Networks”) according to which *“Current TNs have different websites with different IT structures, formats and contents, depending on the actors involved in the project, the theme, the sector, the targeted audience and countries and the outputs of the project”* (Marois et al., 2019). Regarding the access to data, there are two approaches: (i) data made available from the TN’s website; and (ii) data accessible from dedicated databases.

EURAKNOS aspires to develop and deliver a **High Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR)**; in other words, a collection of data objects from TNs with an increased importance to the end-users targeted (namely, farmers, foresters, and advisors). Apart from being relevant, data should also be easily accessible and findable (Marois et al., 2019). Therefore, the development of the HIKR of EURAKNOS needs to be based on technologies that are compliant with open data standards and have the capacity to facilitate access by both human and machine agents. However, accessibility and findability are two core features that need to be built on a robust conceptual design. So, the basic pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR, as shown in Figure 2 below, are:

- a robust conceptual design (i.e., the EURAKNOS data model);
- the accessibility and findability of the data provided;
- the availability of data that is important and useful to the end-user types targeted; and
- the adoption of state-of-the-art technologies that comply with open data standards and are able to facilitate access to data by both human and machine agents.

Figure 2: Basic pillars of the EURAKNOS HIKR

Based on the above, the EURAKNOS HIKR is going to have a state-of-the-art data repository at its core, where data will be stored according to the data model presented in the following section. It needs to be stressed that the term “data repository” holds a different meaning than that of “database”, despite the fact that these terms are sometimes used interchangeably. A database is “*an organised collection of data, generally stored and accessed electronically from a computer system*”⁷, whereas the term “data repository” relates to technologies of a broader scope by emphasising on data management and data curation⁸ issues. More specifically, a data repository can be conceptualised as a database-related infrastructure providing solutions for data collection and management with regard to a wide spectrum of purposes⁹. By taking account of the basic pillars on which the EURAKNOS HIKR needs to be built, as well as the feedback received at the Paris meeting’s workshop, the technology solution to be employed for the development of the EURAKNOS data repository, based on the library metaphor as stated in the first phase of the evolutionary path towards a future, fully-fledged digital platform (see section 7), is **DSpace**¹⁰.

4.2 The EURAKNOS data model

4.2.1 What is a data model, and why is it needed?

The data objects that have been created and disseminated by TNs, which are intended to be integrated into the EURAKNOS repository, are heterogeneous in regard to their categories and format. Apart from that, there is limited to zero evidence relating to the data models employed by TNs. Thus, the provision of content and information of relevance and importance to the end-user types targeted in EURAKNOS

⁷ <https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Database>

⁸ According to Wikipedia (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_curation), data curation is “*the organisation and integration of data collected from various sources*” and involves processes of “*annotation, publication and presentation of the data such that the value of the data is maintained over time, and the data remains available for reuse and preservation.*”

⁹ <https://digitalguardian.com/blog/what-data-repository>

¹⁰ More details are made available in the “Technology framework” section.

(namely, farmers, foresters, and advisors) needs to be based on a robust conceptual design (i.e., a data model) explicitly illustrating how data is structured. A data model is “*an abstract model that organises elements of data and standardises how they relate to one another and to the properties of real-world entities.*”¹¹ As stated above, there is a big heterogeneity in the data objects available from the TN KRs. Thus, in order to collect, store, and enable access to this variety of data objects (from the EURAKNOS HIKR) in a homogeneous way, there is a need for a formal description of the **kinds of data objects** and the respective **formats in which content and information is being conveyed** by them, the **data object types** available, as well as the **purposes that the various data objects serve**. The aim of the EURAKNOS data model is to **capture** and **formally describe** the **entities, relations, and properties** that frame the context within which the various TNs produce (and disseminate) their digital outputs (the data objects available from their KRs). This way, the EURAKNOS data model will serve as the basis for the definition of the metadata to describe the data objects in the EURAKNOS repository.

4.2.2 How can Thematic Networks work with the EURAKNOS HIKR?

By providing a well-structured, formal description of the entities, entity properties, and entity relations of importance for an adequate description of the TNs’ digital outputs, the EURAKNOS data model aims to become a legacy outcome of the project for the TN community.

Figure 3: Scenarios illustrating the potential contribution of the EURAKNOS data model and repository to future Thematic Network efforts

As shown in Figure 3 above, there are three different scenarios illustrating the potential contribution of the EURAKNOS data model (and repository) to future Thematic Network efforts:

- **Scenario #1:** A Thematic Network can *consume data available from the EURAKNOS repository* via the use of the EURAKNOS Application Programming Interface (API)¹² described in Deliverable 4.2 (“**API documentation**”).
- **Scenario #2:** A Thematic Network can have its own KR, but its data objects are also stored into the EURAKNOS HIKR based on the EURAKNOS data model.

¹¹ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Data_model

¹² According to Wikipedia (), an Application Programming Interface (API) is “*a computing interface to a software component or a system, that defines how other components or systems can use it*” by defining the “*kinds of calls or requests that can be made, how to make them, the data formats that should be used, the conventions to follow, etc.*”

- **Scenario #3:** A Thematic Network can *maintain its own KR* to store (and disseminate) data objects by *making use* of the (appropriately adapted/extended) *EURAKNOS data model*.

4.2.3 Requirements for the EURAKNOS data model

Before proceeding to the presentation and explanation of the EURAKNOS data model, we need to start from the requirements on which all the model-related design decisions and choices have been made. At the top level, the input for the identification and definition of requirements for the EURAKNOS data model has been provided by the conclusions and recommendations drawn from the results of the work reported in Deliverable 2.1 (“Report on content and structures of data provision & knowledge formats of TNs”) (Mosquera Losada et al., 2019), Deliverable 2.2 (“Report on format and design of knowledge reservoirs of Thematic Networks”) (Marois et al., 2019), and Deliverable 3.1 (“HIKR data best practices and methodologies”) (Marois et al., 2020).

More specifically, the points listed below summarise the main conclusions made from the desk analysis of the digital content/information available from the KRs of the TNs (reported in **Deliverable 2.1**) and the implications of those conclusions for the decisions and choices related to the data model:

- Regarding the organisations involved either as coordinators or partners in the TNs, there is a strong representation of countries in the central and western Europe (e.g., UK, Germany, France, Spain). Countries from the eastern part of Europe are less represented.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Need to consider entity properties allowing to capture: (i) the country/geographic location that the content of a data object relates to; and (ii) the data object’s content language.
- Most of the TNs are dealing with arable crops, livestock, and agroforestry/forestry.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (i.e., the “source” of the data objects) relates to, and the topics of the various data objects, by considering the appropriate entities, relations and entity properties in the data model.
- Most of the TNs target cooperatives, family, and collective farming.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.
- Overall, the existing TNs, and the data objects created in their context, are about fertilisation, water management, farming systems, treatment of illnesses, and value chain development and business modelling.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entities, relations and entity properties in the data model.
- Overall, the TNs have created communication and dissemination material falling into a total number of 24 categories. The most popular categories are Practice Abstracts and factsheets. Podcasts and videos appear to be the least popular categories.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Identify and define categories/kinds of data objects and the types of the data objects available per category/kind (the kinds of the data objects available from the TN KRs that are reported in Deliverable 2.1 are not based on some standard taxonomy/categorisation).

The conclusions that have been made as part of the analysis reported in **Deliverable 2.2**, as well as the set of the recommendations provided, together with their implications for the design of the data model are listed below:

- Current TNs have different websites with different IT structures, formats and contents depending upon the actors involved in the project, the theme, the sector, the targeted audience and countries,

and the outputs of the project. To be of high impact, the results should not only be of high relevance to the end-user, but also easily accessible and understandable. This should be better facilitated.

- **Implications for the data model design:** Design a data model that will allow for the definition of metadata for the adequate description of the data objects in the EURAKNOS HIKR. This metadata will provide contextual information for each data object enabling the end-users to easily identify the appropriateness and relevance (of the data objects) to their interests and needs.
- The sustainability of the website is a key issue in terms of long-term impact. Therefore, a generic website or platform may be created with short descriptions and links to the individual project websites, which are built in a common format.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the “source” TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
- When designing a KR, it is absolutely essential and fundamental to take into account the need and to satisfy the expectations of end-users. We must be able to know what type of content end-users expect and to define the functionalities offered by the KR in order to direct end-users as much as possible and as well as possible towards suitable and interesting content.
- It is also essential to support end-users in their navigation in the KR and it is also important to think about finding a way to make the most appropriate content as easily accessible as possible.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Design a data model that will allow for the definition of metadata for the adequate description of the data objects in the EURAKNOS HIKR. This metadata will provide contextual information for each data object enabling the end-users to easily identify the appropriateness and relevance (of the data objects) to their interests and needs.

Finally, the report of **Deliverable 3.1** provides a list of recommendations regarding the collection and delivery of digital content and information from a HIKR. These recommendations, and the implications for the data model’s design associated with them, are the following:

- Identify the needs of the end-users and also identify what the end-users expect from the TNs’ KR in terms of: (i) kind of knowledge (e.g., topics related to the environment, topics related to current or future regulations, or topics that provide answers on the socio-economic context; and (ii) format of content.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Need to capture the domain/sector a TN relates to, the topics of the data objects, and the variety of formats in which the data objects become available.
- In order to build, design and develop a KR, it is first necessary to define a context. The context is defined by the circumstances and conditions that are part of its environment.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Design a data model that will allow for the definition of metadata for the adequate description of the data objects in the EURAKNOS HIKR. This metadata will provide contextual information for each data object enabling the end-users to easily identify the appropriateness and relevance (of the data objects) to their interests and needs.
- Identify the target users to be reached.
 - **Implications for the data model design:** Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.

Based on the above, the requirements that have driven the design decisions and choices made for the EURAKNOS data model are listed below:

- Design a data model that will allow for the definition of metadata for the adequate description of the data objects in the EURAKNOS HIKR. This metadata will provide contextual information for each data object enabling the end-users to easily identify the appropriateness and relevance (of the data objects) to their interests and needs.
- Identify and define categories/kinds of data objects and the types of the data objects available per category/kind.
- Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (namely, the “source” of data objects) relates to by considering the appropriate entites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
- Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
- Need to capture the the variety of formats in which the data objects become available.
- Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the “source” TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
- Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.
- Need to consider entity properties allowing to capture: (i) the country/geographic location that the content of a data object relates to; and (ii) the data object’s content language.

4.2.4 Shedding light onto the state of knowledge demand and supply

Making informed decisions about the categories/kinds and the types/formats of the data objects to be captured in the EURAKNOS data model requires insights into what the state of knowledge demand is. In other words, insights into the **data object types** and **formats mostly preferred** by the categories of end-users targeted in EURAKNOS. **Farmers, foresters** and **advisors** are considered as the core end-user categories for the e-KRP. However, in the analysis of platform-related initiatives, available at both the international and national levels, made by Gernert et al. (2019), **educators** and **policy-makers** are also identified as end-user categories worth considering. In order to reach conclusions about the types and formats of content preferred by the end-user categories targeted by the e-KRP, we have drawn on the results of the work done in Tasks 3.1 and 4.1. Both tasks have been concerned with efforts to link the needs of the end-users with specific data object types/formats.

Task 3.1 focusses upon the best methodologies and practices to produce, select, collect, and store data as outputs of TNs, and is also concerned with the identification of data object types and formats that should be considered for a HIKR. Task 4.1 has been concerned with the investigation of the feasibility, as well as the added value, of a new, centralised agriculture-related digital platform. For this purpose, a systematic mapping and analysis of existing platform-related initiatives, available both at the national and international levels, has taken place with a focus on knowledge-driven needs of users. The process from the identification of end-user categories of interest to the e-KRP to the integration of data objects from a sample of eight (8) TNs into the EURAKNOS HIKR is shown in Figure 4 below.

The EURAKNOS meeting in Paris (12-13 December, 2019) hosted a workshop dedicated to the aim and activities of Task 3.1 (Working Group 3.1 workshop) in the context of which, experts were invited to provide their inputs regarding the evaluation of the data available by the KRs of TNs and contribute to the establishment of the criteria for selecting the content to become available from a HIKR. According to the workshop outcomes reported by Marois et al. (2020), a HIKR should primarily target at the needs of farmers and advisors who have been identified as major end-user types. Based on that, there needs to be a core focus on the provision of **data objects conveying practical and ready-to-apply knowledge**.

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However, the **information available to end-users** should also **reflect research findings** that have been appropriately tested and validated. **Booklets, videos and brochures** have been proposed as data object categories that should be considered for the delivery of content and information to the end-users with **videos being considered as more appealing to farmers**. Content produced by peers is highly valued by farmers and, thus, should be also provided by a HIKR. Providing content and information in languages other than English has also been brought up as an issue of importance.

Figure 4: Process from the identification of the e-KRP end-user categories to the integration of TN data objects into the EURAKNOS HIKR

The need to **provide farmers with ready-to-apply, practical and comprehensible information** has also been highlighted by Gernert et al. (2019), who have made an alignment between different categories/types of end-users and their needs in terms of agriculture-related knowledge (shown in Table 1 below).

Table 1: Alignment between end-user types and their needs in terms of Agriculture-related knowledge (adapted from Gernert et al., 2019)

	Characteristics of knowledge needed	Characteristics of content needed	Types/formats of data conveying the knowledge and content required
Farmer	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - easily accessible - comprehensible - useful, practical - up-to-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tailor-made advice - technical knowledge to be applied in the farm - able to be adapted to their context and needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - practice abstracts - video-based material - factsheets - newsletters - training material - farmer magazines/journals
Advisor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - tailor-made - comprehensive - transferable - up-to-date 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - recent policy- and sector-related developments - localised solutions for specific business and technical problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - practice abstracts - newsletters - factsheets - press releases - video-based material

Educator	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - up-to-date - transferable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - scientific results and practice - adapted to the target group and practitioner needs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - practice abstracts - factsheets - training courses/course modules - teacher guides - resource packs
Policy-maker	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - standardised/generalised - evidence-based - up-to-date - applicable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - relevant to their respective policy area - design of new policies 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - press releases - video-based material - newsletters - factsheets - policy reports & recommendations

As made evident from the table above, **practice abstracts, factsheets, newsletters and press releases**, as well as **video-based material** constitute types and formats of data objects that have been identified as **the most relevant** to the needs of **farmers and advisors**. In their majority, these types and formats are also appropriate for addressing the needs of **educators and policy-makers**.

In order to strengthen the insights available from the work done in Tasks 3.1 and 4.1, insights into the types and formats of the data objects to be considered for the EURAKNOS HIKR have also been drawn based on the results of the advisor survey¹³ that took place in the context of the EUFRAS meeting¹⁴ in Athens. The survey took place on the 25th of February 2020 and was implemented by administering questionnaires to a sample of 32 advisors. From the survey questions, those of relevance to the scope of Task 3.2 were the following:

- **Q1:** What kind of content/information would you prefer?
- **Q2:** Which of the following formats of digital content is most preferable to you?

Figure 5: Advisor responses to the question “What kind of content/information would you prefer?”

As shown in Figure 5 above, presentations of innovative and best practices are the most popular kinds of information/content among advisors by receiving a response rate of 28.7% and 25.5% respectively.

¹³ More details with regard to the advisor survey are provided in Annex 3.

¹⁴ <http://www.eufras.eu/index.php/activities/archive/142-eufras-annual-assembly-2020>

Training and educational material is also important, by receiving a response rate of 21.3%, followed by content related to guidelines with a response rate of 17%. Information material has been rated as the least preferred kind of content/information (response rate = 7.4%). For reasons of clarification, it needs to be mentioned that the respondents were able to select more than one options related to the kinds of information and content they prefer.

Regarding Q2, video has been reported as the most preferable content format by receiving a response rate of 27.1%. Video is followed by presentation-based (25.7%) and text-based content (22.9%). Images (14.3%) and audio-based material (7.1%) are the least preferable digital content formats for advisors. The results obtained for Q2 are shown in Figure 6 below.

Figure 6: Advisor responses to the question “Which of the following formats of digital content is most preferable to you?”

To better illustrate the preferences of advisors in agriculture-related content and information, Table 2 below provides an alignment between advisors’ preferences¹⁵ and digital output formats that are most likely to match the preferences reported.

Table 2: Alignment between advisors’ preferences and the most relevant kinds and types of outputs proposed in the data model

Preferred kind of content/information	Format of digital output
Presentation of innovative/best practice	Audio, text, presentation (slideshow), video
Education/training material	Audio, text, presentation (slideshow), video
Guidelines	Audio, text, presentation (slideshow), video

The insights about the data object types and formats that could be of relevance to the end-users, can be summed up to the following points:

- Content and information delivered through **video-based data objects** is **preferred the most by all the types of end-users targeted**.

¹⁵ In order to focus on the most preferable kinds of content/information, those rated below 10% (i.e. “information material”) have not been considered.

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- There is a **range of content and information** provided in **text-based format** (e.g., practice abstracts, guides, factsheets, booklets, handbooks, brochures, tutorials, education and training material, manuals) that **has the capacity to cover the needs** of the end-users targeted; documents are a kind of digital output that is highly valued by both farmers and advisors.
- Evidence for **preferences in slideshow-based content/information** (i.e., presentations) **is available only for advisors**. Advisors are more in favour of slideshow-based material than information and content delivered in a textual format.
- Information on **preferences in image-based and audio-based content and information** is available **only for advisors**. By taking account of their preferences in content and information related to best and innovative practices, as well as guidelines, it can be concluded that audio-based material (e.g., podcasts) conveying such kinds of information would be relevant to advisors' needs.

On top of the conclusions listed above, there are some additional points to consider:

- There is a requirement to have data objects from a sample of eight (8) Thematic Networks into the EURAKNOS repository as a proof of concept for the e-KRP design and development.
- Evidence for preferences in slideshow-based (i.e., presentations), as well as image- and audio-based content and information is only available for advisors. However, we may assume that these kinds/formats of digital outputs could also be of relevance to farmers and foresters (by taking account of the tight interactions between advisors and farmers/foresters).
- The majority of digital outputs provided by TNs relates to types associated with text-based formats (e.g., practice abstracts, factsheets, press releases, research/technical articles, handbooks, reports, and guides). Video-based content and information is available at a lower rate (it counts for 41.7% of the digital outputs available). The same applies to image-based content and information, as well as podcasts (i.e., audio-based content and information) which count for 33.3% and 20.8% of the total content respectively (Mosquera Losada et al., 2019).

Given the above, a **rough order** (in terms of preference/priority) **of the data object formats to consider** for the repository of the EURAKNOS prototype e-KRP is the following:

1. **videos** of any type;
2. **documents** with an emphasis on types like practice abstracts, factsheets, tutorials, manuals, guides, handbooks, technical articles, booklets, brochures, newsletters, press releases, journal articles, chapters in edited volumes, articles in conference proceedings, deliverable reports, reports/papers, and books¹⁶;
3. **presentations**: there will be an attempt to emphasise upon types such as guides, tutorials, and educational/training presentations. In the case that such types of presentation-based outputs are not available, then any type available will be collected and integrated in the HIKR.
4. **images** of any type;
5. **audio-based outputs**: there will be an attempt to emphasise upon types like educational and training podcasts, on-demand seminars, and guides. In the case that such types of audio-based outputs are not available, then any type available will be collected and integrated in the HIKR.

¹⁶ By taking account of the fact that articles in conference proceedings, books, chapters in edited volumes, deliverable reports, journal articles, and reports/papers are not the most preferable types of data by the e-KRP end-user types, only a few data objects from this subset will be collected and stored into the HIKR.

The order of the data object kinds provided above is indicative of the relative importance of each kind of output (in comparison to the rest of the output kinds) based on the end-user preferences (see Figure 7 below).

Figure 7: Kinds of TN outputs to be considered for the repository of the prototype e-KRP (the box heights are indicative of the relative importance of each output kind based on end-user preferences)

4.2.5 Description of the EURAKNOS data model

Storing the digital outputs of TNs into the EURAKNOS repository (i.e., the HIKR) and delivering them to the end-users in a homogeneous way necessitates the adoption of a data model. The data model needs to include the definitions of entities, relations between entities, and entity attributes helping to frame the context related to TN outputs. The main goal of proposing and using a data model is to determine a list of metadata for an adequate description of the digital outputs (i.e., the data objects) of TNs. The data model, which is core to the EURAKNOS repository design, takes the form of an ontology presented below. Despite the heterogeneity in the categories/kinds and the formats/types in which the various TNs make their digital outputs available, as well as the range of structures employed for the delivery of content and information from their KRs, the EURAKNOS data model provides **a means of effective and efficient description** of the various digital outputs available.

The aim of this section is to present and describe the EURAKNOS data model and also outline the steps of the methodology followed for its development. The creation of the EURAKNOS data model has been based on the broadly acknowledged and widely adopted methodology of Noy and McGuiness (2001), which is considered a **straightforward, baseline approach** consisting of well-defined steps allowing for a **top-down ontology development**. The steps of the methodology are shown in Figure 8 below. The reason for deciding to adopt the methodology of Noy and McGuiness is its **straightforward nature** and **stepwise approach to ontology building**, able to be **understood** and **followed** by non-technical audiences as well (given the EURAKNOS’s aspiration to provide its data model to future TNs as a legacy outcome, for further uptake, regardless of whether they opt to disseminate their data objects directly through the e-KRP or build their own repositories). The Noy and McGuiness’s methodology divides the ontology building work into well-organised and self-contained tasks gradually leading to **decisions on the entities to define** and their **grouping into hierarchies**, as well as the **relations that hold between the entities** towards **satisfying the data model-related requirements**.

Figure 8: The steps of the methodology of Noy and McGuiness (2001) adopted for building the EURAKNOS data model

Detailed accounts of the activities executed per methodology phase, are provided next.

4.2.5.1 The EURAKNOS data model in a nutshell

The EURAKNOS data model is shown in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9: The EURAKNOS data model

The model shown above is an explicit illustration of how the structuring of data has been conceived in EURAKNOS by taking account of the diversity of TN digital outputs. It serves as the basis for determining the metadata elements required for effectively and efficiently describing the TN outputs that are going to be housed in the EURAKNOS repository (i.e., the HIKR). A core element in the EURAKNOS data model is that of a **class**. Classes are abstract constructs used to denote collections of individuals, objects, or concepts that share similar attributes. For instance, the class `Output` denotes **any digital output** (i.e., data object) that may have been produced by a TN, rather than a specific data object. In the illustration of the EURAKNOS data model, in Figure 9 above, classes are represented as rectangles. An **instance is a specific manifestation of a class**; in other words, a concrete representative of that class. The **SMART-AKIS** Thematic Network is, for example, specific TN that constitutes an instance of the EURAKNOS data model's `ThematicNetwork` class.

Properties are also a key element of the data model. We distinguish between two types of properties; namely, the **datatype properties** and **object properties**. More specifically, the datatype properties are **properties receiving data values** (e.g., strings, integers, Boolean values, double-precision floating point numbers). The values of object properties are **class instances**. Object properties are also referred to as **relations**. In our data model, the relations that hold between classes (i.e., the object properties) are shown as edges connecting two rectangles. The black triangles are a design convention used to indicate the relation's direction. For reasons of simplicity, the diagrammatic illustration of the EURAKNOS data model contains only the object properties. Analytical descriptions of both the object and the datatype properties are provided next and in Annex 1 of the report.

Another piece of information available in the data model is that of the **cardinality/multiplicity** of object properties, provided in the form of (minimum, maximum) value ranges¹⁷. It is used to show the number of class instances associated with an instance of the opposite side. For example, one instance of the `Individual` class may be `affiliatedWith` one or more instances of the `Organisation` class and vice versa.

A point that is worth attention is that some classes (namely, the `Output` and `Creator` classes) have been labelled as `Abstract`. **Abstract classes** do not have direct instances; only their subclasses do. So, a specific individual (i.e., a person) that has been involved in the creation of an output is an instance of the `Individual` subclass and is not considered to be a direct instance of the `Creator` class.

The diagrammatic illustration of the EURAKNOS data model is based on the modelling conventions of the **UML (Unified Modelling Language)**¹⁸ **class diagram**. Class diagrams are tools commonly employed for illustrating ontologies, because of a number of similarities in the modelling conventions employed. However, there are significant differences as well. Therefore, **Ontology UML Profiles** are extensions of the set of design elements and conventions used in a UML class diagram, which have been proposed¹⁹ to efficiently address ontology-related particularities. The EURAKNOS data model has been created by making use of a bare minimum set of UML-related model elements to enhance the interpretability and comprehensibility of the design. For the same reason, no UML profile add-ons have been used except from the «`OntClass`» tag that is used to denote that the model's classes are ontology classes.

The EURAKNOS data model is made available in RDF/XML syntax in Annex 2 and has been published in Zenodo. The data model (**version 1.0 of the EURAKNOS data model**) is released under the **Creative Commons “Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)”**²⁰ license, by following the **guidelines of the OBO Foundry**²¹ according to which an ontology must be “*openly available to be used by all without any constraint other than (a) its origin must be acknowledged and (b) it is not to be altered and subsequently redistributed in altered form under the original name or with the same identifiers.*” The data model's documentation can be accessed from the EURAKNOS project's GitLab repository (<https://gitlab.euraknos.cf/>).

4.2.5.2 The EURAKNOS data model's creation process

STEP 1 – Determine the domain and scope of the ontology

The first step in the data model building process is about framing the context of the modelling task. It entails the **specification of the model's purpose**, as well as the **identification of key questions** (known as competency questions) **that the model should provide answers for**. The purpose of the EURAKNOS data model is to **provide a structure**, capturing and formally describing entities, entity properties, and relations of importance for the **identification and definition of the metadata** for **describing** the various data objects to be stored into the EURAKNOS repository. The **competency questions** listed below help make the purpose of the data model more explicit:

- What kinds of data objects are available from project X?
- What are the domains of the Thematic Networks from which data objects of the type X have been made available?

¹⁷ It is worth to be mentioned that the * cardinality-related notation is equivalent to the **0..*** notation (which means greater than or equal to zero).

¹⁸ **UML (Unified Modelling Language)** is a general-purpose, developmental, modelling language used in the field of software engineering, which is intended to provide a standard way to visualise the design of a system (Booch et al., 2005).

¹⁹ See, Baclawski et al. (2001) and Djurić et al. (2004) for reference.

²⁰ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

²¹ <http://www.obofoundry.org/principles/fp-001-open.html>

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- What are the topics of the data objects available from project X?
- Which are the organisations involved in the creation of data objects of the type X, which have been made available from the Thematic Network Y?
- What are the types of data objects intended to be used by end-users of the type X?
- What are the data objects of type X available from project Y, in relation to the geographic location Z?

STEP 2 – Consider reusing existing ontologies

Noy and McGuinness (2001) explicitly articulate that “*reusing existing ontologies may be a requirement if our system needs to interact with other applications that have already committed to particular ontologies or controlled vocabularies.*” (p. 6). Re-using concepts and relations defined in and available from existing ontologies helps towards facilitating processes of data and information interoperability and exchange. This is of particular importance when considering machine agents as consumers of data and information. The need for enabling and enhancing the interoperability of data and information is emphasised in the FAIR Data principles (Wilkinson et al., 2016), which have gained traction in the last few years as a good data sharing practice.

The ontology considered in our data modelling task for the needs of re-using concepts and relations is **Schema.org**²². It is a **generic ontology** that has been considered for the re-use of classes relating to the kinds/categories of the data objects considered in EURAKNOS (e.g., text, audio, video, image), as well as other entities of importance to the data model. It has also been used as a point of reference for the identification of properties able to model **basic descriptive features** of data objects (e.g., the content language, links of the content with specific geographic locations, etc). Details about the components of Schema.org that have been re-used in the construction of the EURAKNOS data model are provided in the descriptions of the methodology steps coming next.

STEP 3 – Enumerate important terms in the ontology

The aim of this step has been to **identify a list of key terms**, as well as **relationships between the terms** identified, which would **help define our model’s classes, class relations, and class properties**. To do so, we have started from an attempt to provide a **detailed definition** of the Thematic Network concept. The basic assumption underpinning this endeavour is that the identification of the data model’s core elements (namely, the entities, entity attributes, and relations between entities) necessitates an **explicit definition of the concept of Thematic Networks**.

Thematic Networks constitute a particular format of Multi-Actor projects, promoted by the agricultural European Innovation Partnership (EIP-AGRI)²³ and funded by EU’s Horizon 2020 programme²⁴, which focus on a specific theme. They bring together actors from both science and practice with the purpose to collect and disseminate useful, practical outputs. Thematic Networks have stemmed from the need to efficiently address agriculture- and forestry-related problems and identify innovative solutions and best practices. However, solutions need to occur as the outcome of coordinated, joint efforts of various actors bringing different perspectives and values to the process and, thus, contributing to synergies between research and practice. This approach is core to what EIP-AGRI calls an “*interactive innovation model*”²⁵ and constitutes the foundation of Multi-Actor projects (EIP-AGRI, 2017). Thematic Networks are a particular format of Multi-Actor projects (EIP-AGRI, 2016) and as such they:

²² <https://schema.org/>

²³ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en>

²⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/what-horizon-2020>

²⁵ <https://ec.europa.eu/eip/agriculture/en/eip-agri-concept>

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- relate to specific themes (e.g., sustainable cropping systems, animal production systems, plant health, rural dynamics and policies, knowledge and innovation systems) and focus on real problems of practitioners;
- bring together partners with complementary backgrounds and expertise to collaborate, throughout the entire project lifecycle, and come up with innovative solutions; and
- collect, further develop, as well as disseminate ready-to-apply recommendations and practices and, thus, serve as multipliers of Agriculture-related knowledge.

These distinctive features of Thematic Networks have provided the necessary input for developing the following, integrated definition of the concept of Thematic Networks:

Thematic networks are multi-actor projects that focus on a **theme**. The theme of a Thematic Network relates to a **domain**. Thematic Networks aim to disseminate easy to understand and apply information in the form of useful, practical **outputs** (practice abstracts, manuals, reports, infographics, videos, etc.). Outputs available by a Thematic Network can be distinguished into documents, software applications, presentations, images, audio and video objects, and datasets. Outputs are made available to end-users (e.g., farmers, foresters, advisors) and have specific **types** and **formats**. Each output has a **purpose** (i.e., a reason for which it has been created), a **topic** (relevant to the Thematic Network’s domain) and has been created by a **creator**. Creators can be distinguished into **organisations** and **individuals** (who are affiliated with organisations). Organisations are involved in Thematic Networks either as **participating** or **leading** partners.

From the definition provided above, a number of statements can be extracted. These statements help identify entities, relations between entities, and entity attributes. In these statements (listed below), potential entity and entity attribute mentions are highlighted with the help of bold characters. Relation mentions are highlighted in italicised characters.

- A **Thematic Network** *is about* a **theme**, and the **theme** *relates to* a **domain**. As a consequence, a **Thematic Network** *relates to* a **domain**.
- An **output** (available by a Thematic Network) is intended to be *used by* (specific **types of**) **end users**.
- There are different *kinds of* outputs: documents, software applications, presentations, audio and video objects, images, and datasets.
- An output *has* a {topic, purpose, type, format}.
- An output is *created by* a creator. A creator *is* an individual or organisation²⁶.
- An **individual** *is affiliated with* an **organisation**.
- An **organisation** has a specific type of involvement in the Thematic Network (namely, participating or leading partner).

This analysis has yielded a pool of terms to be considered for the definition of the data model’s entities and/or entity attributes. These terms are the following:

- | | | | |
|----------|---------------|--------------|--------------------|
| • Domain | • Output type | • Format | • Organisation |
| • Topic | • End-user | • Purpose | • Thematic Network |
| • Output | • Creator | • Individual | |

Furthermore, there is a list of relationship mentions between terms that have been identified and that can be considered as potential relations between classes, namely:

- | | | |
|--------------|-------------|---------------|
| • relates to | • has topic | • has purpose |
| • used by | • has type | • created by |

²⁶ This statement can also be formulated as follows: “An **individual** and an **organisation** are *kinds of* **creator**.”

- kind of
- has format
- affiliated with

STEP 4 – Define the classes and the class hierarchy

A critical step in the construction of the EURAKNOS data model has been the **identification of classes and class hierarchies**. The specification of the classes and class hierarchies in our data model has been based on the terms of importance described above. In addition, the **state of knowledge demand and supply** outlined in Section 4.2.4 (“Shedding light onto the state of knowledge demand and supply”) has also helped to make decisions about the classes to include and define in the data model. To begin with, there needs to be an adequate description of the various **kinds** of the digital outputs produced by TNs and the respective **formats** in which content and information is conveyed, the **types** of the data objects available, and the **purpose** that a data object has. These are **specific properties** of the “Output” entity, which needs to be modelled as a class in the EURAKNOS data model. “Thematic Network”, “Domain” (i.e., the agricultural sector a TN relates to), “Topic” (i.e., the issue(s) a TN output is about), “Creator” (distinguished into “Individual” and “Organisation”), and “End User Type” are the entities that have been identified as significant for the effective and efficient capture of the context in which the digital outputs of Thematic Networks are produced and get disseminated.

On top of that, it needs to be highlighted that the TN outputs will be stored and become available from the EURAKNOS repository as digital files. Based on the work documented in Deliverable 2.1 (Mosquera Losada et al., 2019), and given the variety of the output categories/kinds both in demand and supply, the kinds of outputs proposed in the EURAKNOS data model are: **documents, presentations, images, software applications, audio and video objects, datasets**. These kinds have been derived from the list of media types defined by the Internet Assigned Numbers Authority²⁷ (the so-called Multipurpose Internet Mail Extensions or MIME types). The media types in that list are: *application, audio, example, font, image, message, model, text and video*. From that list, the media types that are relevant for determining the kinds of TN outputs are: *application, audio, image, text and video*. The *presentation* and *dataset* kinds have been added to fully capture the range of TN outputs considered in EURAKNOS.

Based on the above, the classes included in the EURAKNOS data model are: *Output, EndUserType, Creator, ThematicNetwork, Topic, Domain, Audio, Dataset, Software, Document, Presentation, Image, Video, Individual, and Organisation*. The definition of several classes in the EURAKNOS data model is based on class definitions available in **Schema.org**, which is a “*collaborative, community activity with a mission to create, maintain, and promote schemas for structured data on the Internet, on web pages, in email messages, and beyond.*”²⁸ Table 3 below lists all the classes included in the EURAKNOS data model, the Schema.org class definitions re-used (where applicable), and the data model-related requirements addressed.

Table 3: Classes included in the EURAKNOS data model, the Schema.org classes re-used and the model-related requirements addressed

Class in the EURAKNOS data model	Schema.org class re-used	Requirement addressed
Output	-	Identify and define categories/kinds of data objects and the types of the data objects available per category/kind.
Audio	schema:AudioObject URI: https://schema.org/AudioObject	
Dataset	schema:Dataset URI: https://schema.org/Dataset	
Document	schema:TextDigitalDocument URI: https://schema.org/TextDigitalDocument	

²⁷ <https://www.iana.org/>

²⁸ <https://schema.org/>

Image	schema : ImageObject URI : https://schema.org/ImageObject	
Presentation	schema : PresentationDigitalDocument URI : https://schema.org/PresentationDigitalDocument	
Software	schema : SoftwareApplication URI : https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication	
Video	schema : VideoObject URI : https://schema.org/VideoObject	
Creator	-	Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the “source” TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
Individual	schema : Person URI : https://schema.org/Person	
Organisation	schema : Organization URI : https://schema.org/Organization	
ThematicNetwork	-	
Domain	-	Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (namely, the “source” of data objects) relates to by considering the appropriate entities, relations and entity properties in the data model.
Topic	-	Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entities, relations and entity properties in the data model.
EndUserType	-	Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.

A specific type of relation is the one that links a **subclass** to its **parent class**. Subclasses are linked to their parent classes by an “**is-a**” relationship. The notation used for this relationship type is an arrow with a non-filled triangle at its end linking the subclass to its parent class.

Figure 10: Hierarchical structure in the EURAKNOS data model making explicit the different kinds of data objects

In the EURAKNOS data model there are **two hierarchical structures**. More specifically, the `Audio`, `Dataset`, `Presentation`, `Software`, `Document`, `Image`, and `Video` classes are all subclasses of the abstract `Output` class (see Figure 10 above). This distinction is being made to efficiently capture and model the various kinds of the data objects considered in EURAKNOS. Similarly, the `Individual` and `Organisation` classes have been modelled as subclasses of the `Creator` class. By making this design choice, we are able to consider cases in which the entitie(s) behind the creation of a data object is either a person or an organisation. This hierarchical structure is shown in Figure 11 below.

Figure 11: Hierarchical structure making explicit the different kinds of data object creators considered in the data model

STEP 5 – Define the properties of classes

In the terminology introduced by the Web Ontology Language (OWL) specification there are two kinds of properties: (i) **object properties**; and (ii) **datatype properties**.

Object properties

Object properties are used to describe the relationships between class instances. Every object property has one class as its domain and another class as its range. Table 4 below provides a list of all the object properties in the EURAKNOS data model, the domain and range of each object property, as well as the data model-requirements addressed.

Table 4: Object properties included in the EURAKNOS data model, their domain and range, and the data model-requirements addressed

Object property	Domain	Range	Requirement addressed
<code>associatedWith</code>	<code>Topic</code>	<code>Domain</code>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (namely, the “source” of data objects) relates to by considering the appropriate entitites, relations and entity properties in the data model. Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entitites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
<code>affiliatedWith</code>	<code>Individual</code>	<code>Organization</code>	Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in

Object property	Domain	Range	Requirement addressed
coordinatedBy	ThematicNetwork	Organisation	the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the “source” TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
createdBy	Output	Creator	
hasTopic	Output	Topic	Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entitites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
relatesTo	ThematicNetwork	Domain	Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (namely, the “source” of data objects) relates to by considering the appropriate entitites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
usedBy	Output	EndUserType	Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.

The definition of the object properties in the EURAKNOS data model has not been based on the re-use of object properties from external ontologies.

Datatype properties

Datatype properties are **properties receiving data values** such as integers, strings, Boolean values, and double-precision floating point numbers. Tables 5 to 10 list the datatype properties identified for each class of the EURAKNOS data model, together with the properties of the Schema.org ontology that have been re-used (for defining our data model’s datatype properties), and the model-related requirements addressed (where applicable).

Table 5: Datatype properties of the *ThematicNetwork* class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
acronym	schema : alternateName URI: https://schema.org/alternateName	Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the “source” TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
fullName	schema : name URI: https://schema.org/name	
url	schema : url URI: https://schema.org/url	
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	

Table 6: Datatype properties of the *Domain* class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
name	schema : name URI: https://schema.org/name	Need to capture the domain/sector that a TN (namely, the “source” of data objects) relates to by considering the appropriate entitites, relations and entity properties in the data model.
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	

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Table 7: Datatype properties of the *Topic* class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
name	schema : name URI: https://schema.org/name	Need to capture the topics of the various data objects by considering the appropriate entities, relations and entity properties in the data model.
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	

Table 8: Datatype properties of the *Output* class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
title	-	-
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	-
contentInLanguage	schema : inLanguage URI: https://schema.org/inLanguage	Need to consider entity properties allowing to capture the data object's content language.
keywords	schema : keywords URI: https://schema.org/keywords	-
fileUrl	schema : url URI: https://schema.org/url	Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the "source" TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of its creator(s), the date of the data object's creation, etc.).
dateCreated	schema : dateCreated URI: https://schema.org/dateCreated	
license	schema : license URI: https://schema.org/license	-
geographicLocation	schema : contentLocation URI: https://schema.org/contentLocation	Need to consider entity properties allowing to capture the country/ geographic location that the content of a data object relates to.
purpose	schema : potentialAction URI: https://schema.org/potentialAction	-
fileSize	schema : fileSize URI: https://schema.org/fileSize	-

Table 9: Datatype properties of the *EndUser* type class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
name	schema : name URI: https://schema.org/name	Proceed to design decisions that help model the various types of end-users potentially targeted by the EURAKNOS HIKR.
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	

Table 10: Datatype properties of the *Creator* class

Datatype property	Schema.org property re-used	Requirement addressed
name	schema : name URI: https://schema.org/name	Consider entities, relations, and entity properties to be included in the data model that will allow to capture and provide provenance information (e.g., the name of the "source" TN and the domain/sector it relates to, the name of
description	schema : description URI: https://schema.org/description	

		its creator(s), the date of the data object’s creation, etc.).
--	--	--

The `Audio`, `Dataset`, `Document`, `Image`, `Presentation`, `Software` and `Video` classes are subclasses of the `Output` class, which means that all the properties of the `Output` class are inherited by its subclasses. However, the subclasses of the `Output` class have two additional properties. These properties relate to the **type** and **format** of the data objects. These datatype properties are defined in response to the requirement having to do with the need to: (i) identify and define the types of the data objects available per category/kind; and (ii) to capture the variety of formats in which the data objects become available.

Similarly, the `Individual` and `Organisation` classes are subclasses of the `Creator` class. This means that all the properties of the `Creator` class are inherited by its subclasses. However, the two subclasses of the `Creator` class have an additional property as well. This additional property relates to the **type** of the `Individual` or the `Organisation` and has been defined in response to the requirement having to do with the consideration of entities, relations, and entity properties that will allow to capture and provide provenance information.

STEP 6 – Define the facets of the slots

When referring to “*facets of the slots*”, what is meant is the **values** that the datatype properties in our model can take. The values that can be assigned to the datatype properties in our data model together with a short description of each datatype property are available in Annex 1.

STEP 7 – Create instances

According to Noy and McGuinness (2001), the final step in an ontology building process is the creation of class instances. Defining an instance requires to: (i) select a class; (ii) create an individual instance of that class; and (iii) provide values to the instance’s properties. In the remaining part of this section, **we provide the example of a document** (i.e., an instance of the `Document` class) which is a **factsheet** created in the AFINET²⁹ Thematic Network³⁰. This step helps provide a **validation of the data model** by drawing upon a concrete example. Table 11 below shows the values provided to the datatype properties of the selected instance (of the `Document` class), as well as the datatype property values of the class instances that are (directly or indirectly) related to the `Document` class through the EURAKNOS data model’s object properties. These are instances of the `Creator`, `EndUserType`, `Topic`, `Domain`, and `ThematicNetwork` classes.

Table 11: Instances related to the example digital output, the classes they belong to, their datatype properties, and assigned values

Instance	Class the instance belongs to	Datatype property	Value
Data object	Output > Document	title	“Productive Use of the Tree Row Understorey”
		description	“This document is a factsheet created in the context of the AFINET project that gives information about opportunities for crop diversification”

²⁹ <https://agroforestry.net.eu/afinet/>

³⁰ AFINET is a Thematic Network that has been considered as a source of input to the prototype platform built in EURAKNOS (i.e., the e-KRP). Thematic Networks constitute a specific type of MA projects (i.e., they are a subset of MA projects). All the digital outputs collected in EURAKNOS will be part of the digital content to be made available through the EUREKA FarmBook. The factsheet used as an example here is a digital object already housed in the FarmBook.

		contentinLanguage	"English"
		keywords	"diversification", "silvoarable", "tree row", "crops"; "understorey"
		fileUrl	https://euraf.isa.utl.pt/files/pub/20190529_factsheet_14_en_web.pdf
		dateCreated	"2018-03-01"
		licence	https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/
		geographicLocation	"Portugal"
		purpose	"communication"
		fileSize	"1.3 MBs"
		type	"factsheet"
		format	"pdf"
Creator of the data object	Creator > Individual	name	"Maria Rosa Mosquera-Losada"
		description	"The person in lead of the factsheet's creation"
		type	"researcher", "university professor"
Topic of the data object	Topic	name	"Agroforestry"
		description	"The factsheet is about agroforestry"
TN in which the data object has been created	ThematicNetwork	acronym	"AFINET"
		fullname	"Agroforestry Innovation Networks"
		url	https://agroforestrynet.eu/afinet/
		description	"AFINET is a thematic network aimed to foster the exchange and knowledge transfer between scientists and practitioners in the agroforestry. It has acted at the EU level in order to take up research results into practice and to promote innovative ideas to face challenges and resolve problems of practitioners."
Domain of the TN	Domain	name	"Forestry"
		description	"Forestry is the science and craft of creating, managing, planting, using, conserving and repairing forests, woodlands, and associated resources for human and environmental benefits"
Types of end users targeted	EndUserType	name	"foresters", "advisors", "policy maker"
		description	"Three main types of end users are identified as potential recipients of the factsheet."

4.2.6 Compliance with the FAIR Data principles

An issue that is important to consider in the Big Data era is that every publisher can publish information through a data format that is only processable by specific systems. Thus, the resulting data ecosystem becomes less integrated from day to day and this fact that has significant implications with regard to

the discovery and re-use of valuable resources. In order to achieve sustainable data management, the data community has created a set of high-level, technology-agnostic principles known as the **FAIR Data Principles** (Wilkinson et al., 2016). These Principles describe distinct considerations for data publishing to make digital resources **Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable**. Furthermore, because of the information overload experienced by human agents, these principles also emphasise the capacity of computational systems to find, access and reuse data with minimal human intervention. EURAKNOS will undertake these principles by: (i) considering the re-use of components from widely-adopted and broadly acknowledged ontologies (e.g., Schema.org); and (ii) providing a rich set of metadata with the aim to enhance reusability.

4.3 Technology framework

The solution that has been considered and adopted for the needs of the HIKR development is **DSpace**, an “*out-of-the-box open source software package for creating repositories focusing on delivering digital content to end users and providing a full set of tools for managing and preserving content within the application*”³¹. DSpace does not just provide digital file preservation and storage functionalities, but rather goes beyond that and provides functional preservation according to which files are “*kept accessible as technology formats, media and paradigms evolve over time for as many types of files as possible*”³². DSpace is a full-stack web application comprising a database, storage manager, and a front-end web interface.

The reason for selecting DSpace is that it constitutes the most widely adopted data repository creation solution with more than 2,000 installations worldwide³³. It has a vibrant community built around it, it is flexible, and has the capacity to provide solutions to academic and research institutions as “*an open access institutional repository for managing and disseminating scholarly output*”, as well as to other types of organisations for the needs of “*hosting and managing subject-based, dataset or media-based repositories*”³⁴. Integration with OpenAIRE is one of DSpace's core features³⁵. Some indicative project cases that make use of DSpace³⁶ are listed below:

- **Deep Blue**³⁷ is a service from the University of Michigan for providing access to content related to research, teaching, and creativity, which makes use of DSpace as a repository for a range of digital objects including journals.
- Rice University's **TIMEA** initiative³⁸ is a digital archive regarding Western interactions with the Middle East, particularly travels to Egypt during the nineteenth and early twentieth centuries. By making use of a repository built with the help of DSpace, TIMEA allows access to digitised content such as travel guides and narratives, museum catalogues, historical maps, interactive GIS maps of Cyprus and Egypt, as well as photographic and hand-drawn images of Egypt.
- **Policy Archive**³⁹ is a digital library of public policy research containing over 24,000 documents. By making use of a repository, created and maintained with DSpace, the institution provides a digital archive of global, non-partisan public policy research that makes use of the Internet technology to collect and disseminate content related to policy research available in the form of text, video, reports, briefs, and multimedia material.

³¹ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/resources/technical-specifications/>

³² https://duraspace.org/wp-content/uploads/dspace-files/DSpace_Diagram.pdf

³³ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/resources/technical-specifications/>

³⁴ <https://duraspace.org/dspace/resources/technical-specifications/>

³⁵ <https://wiki.lyrasis.org/display/DSPACECRIS/OpenAIRE+Integration>

³⁶ More information about DSpace use cases is available at: <https://duraspace.org/dspace/about/use-cases/>

³⁷ <https://deepblue.lib.umich.edu/>

³⁸ <http://timea.rice.edu/>

³⁹ <https://www.policyarchive.org/>

Other notable cases of open data repositories built on DSpace are the Open Knowledge Repository of World Bank⁴⁰, the Apollo repository of the University of Cambridge⁴¹, the Digital Access to Scholarship initiative of Harvard⁴², DSpace@MIT⁴³, the Spiral repository of the London Imperial College⁴⁴, and the Institutional Repository for Information Sharing of the World Health Organisation (WHO)⁴⁵.

DSpace is the “umbrella” technology solution that is intended to be employed in EURAKNOS. However, there are specific issues that need to be addressed in the context of developing the e-KRP. Such issues relate to data and metadata storage, and search engine functionalities. Given the fact that a detailed description of the EURAKNOS e-KRP’s architecture (in-progress) is beyond the scope of this report⁴⁶, some initial considerations regarding data/metadata storage and potential search engine solutions are provided next.

4.3.1 Data storage

A core component of the DSpace framework is PostgreSQL, an object-relational database used for the item (and metadata) storage. According to its official documentation⁴⁷, PostgreSQL is a highly scalable, SQL-compliant, open source, object-relational database management system with some of its features being the following:

- **Open-source community:** PostgreSQL is the result of a process of fifteen years of development with version 12.2 being the latest one (by the time at which the current report was being drafted).
- **Advanced SQL:** PostgreSQL supports complex queries and ANSI SQL 2003.
- **Extensibility:** PostgreSQL supports a number of advanced data types such as full text and JSON.
- **Freedom:** PostgreSQL comes with a BSD-license allowing to use it for any kind of purpose including commercial exploitation.
- **Languages:** PostgreSQL has an interface with procedures created in widely-adopted programming languages.
- **Concurrency:** Multiple users can concurrently work with the database.

4.3.2 Metadata storage

OpenLink Virtuoso⁴⁸ is a multi-model database that supports, among others, the management of data represented as relational and graph models and is considered as a solution for metadata storage in the context of EURAKNOS. It supports different RDF serializations such as N3 and RDF/XML, as well as the SPARQL Query Language. By being a graph database, OpenLink Virtuoso stores data as a network of objects connected with links between them. This makes OpenLink Virtuoso (and RDF triplestores in general) a choice to consider for managing highly interconnected data, such as metadata. Linked Open Data datasets, like DBpedia and GeoNames, are published, for example, as RDF triplestore databases. This allows for obtaining highly relevant search results from federated queries much faster. Moreover, this type of databases is also capable of handling complex semantic queries and of using inference for uncovering implicit information out of the existing (explicit) relations.

⁴⁰ <https://openknowledge.worldbank.org/>

⁴¹ <https://www.repository.cam.ac.uk/>

⁴² <https://dash.harvard.edu/>

⁴³ <https://dspace.mit.edu/>

⁴⁴ <https://spiral.imperial.ac.uk/index.jsp>

⁴⁵ <https://apps.who.int/iris/>

⁴⁶ Details on the architecture of the EURAKNOS e-KRP will be provided in D4.3 ("EURAKNOS e-KRP documentation and guide").

⁴⁷ https://wiki.postgresql.org/images/4/43/What_is_pg%282%29.pdf

⁴⁸ <https://virtuoso.openlinksw.com/>

4.3.3 Search engine

There are several options that have been examined in regard to the search functionality to be provided in EURAKNOS. These options have not been considered with the aim to replace the search functionality built in DSpace, but rather to complement it. Relational Database Management Systems (RDBMS), such as MySQL, SQLite, PostgreSQL, Microsoft SQL Server, MariaDB etc., are the cornerstone of data persistence in software development. Their longevity, portability, well-written Graphical User Interface tools, and ease of querying, make them the most popular choice for the deployment of data storage mechanisms. The representation of data in a tabular form (i.e., in rows of records and columns of fields) is an intuitive way to organise many transactional data types. As a consequence, it is natural to consider the relational model when trying to organise data for search applications. Yet, modern applications characterised by increased data workloads may suggest that RDBMSs are not scoring very high with regard to providing search functionalities, due to scalability- and speed-related constraints.

Search can be enhanced by using **Solr**⁴⁹, which is the search-related technology shipped with DSpace. Solr is an open-source, enterprise-search platform developed in Java the context of the Apache Lucene project⁵⁰. Solr has the capacity to support efficient querying of data and provide adequate information to the calling component of the system (front-end application). The data stored in the underlying Lucene index will facilitate the search service aspect of the application by storing only searchable views of the data, residing in a decoupled component of system. Some of Solr’s core features are full-text search, hit highlighting, faceted search⁵¹, real-time indexing, dynamic clustering, database integration, NoSQL features, and rich document handling. By allowing for distributed search and index replication, Solr is able to provide scalability and fault tolerance. Solr is widely adopted and used for enterprise search and analytics use cases, and is supported by an active community being responsible for the release of new product versions on a regular basis.

Solr is able to achieve fast search responses by searching an index instead of searching the text directly, which is analogous to making use of a keyword index in the end of a book. This type of index is called **inverted index**⁵², because it inverts the page-centric data structure (page to words) to a keyword-centric data structure (word to pages). Regarding the representation of data, it is a document-based engine, meaning that a document is the basic unit of search and indexing. An index consists of one or more “**Documents**”, and a Document consists of one or more “**Fields**”. In the database terminology, a Document corresponds to a table row, and a Field corresponds to a table column. Before adding documents to Solr, a schema needs to be specified and declare: (i) the kinds of fields available; (ii) the field to be used as the unique/primary key; (iii) the fields required; and (iv) how to index and search each field, as well as the specific field types (e.g., float, long double date text).

To search a document, Apache Solr performs the following operations in sequence:

- **Indexing** – Apache Solr converts the documents into a machine-readable format which is called “Indexing”.
- **Querying** – Relates to the understanding of the terms of a query posed by the user. These terms can be images or keywords.
- **Mapping** – Apache Solr maps the user query to the documents stored in its database in order to find and deliver the most appropriate result(s).
- **Ranking the outcome** – As soon as the engine searches the documents that have been indexed, it proceeds to a ranking of the search results in terms of relevance.

⁴⁹ <https://lucene.apache.org/solr/>

⁵⁰ <https://lucene.apache.org/>

⁵¹ <https://www.sciencedirect.com/topics/computer-science/faceted-search>

⁵² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Inverted_index

Apache Solr runs as a standalone full-text search server. It uses the Lucene Java search library at its core for full-text indexing and search, and has REST-like, HTTP/XML and JSON APIs that make it usable from the most popular programming languages. Documents can be inserted in it ("Indexing") via JSON, XML, CSV or a binary format over HTTP, and queried via HTTP GET. Results can be delivered in JSON, XML, CSV or binary formats. A number of features that make Solr popular and are relevant for the EURAKNOS platform are the following:

- indexing in near real time;
- automated index replication;
- server statistics logging;
- automated failover and recovery;
- rich document parsing and indexing;
- multiple search indexes;
- user-extensible caching;
- design for high-volume traffic;
- scalability, flexibility and extensibility;
- advanced full-text searching;
- geospatial searching; and
- load-balanced querying.

The Apache Solr's basic architecture is shown in Figure 12 below and its major components are⁵³:

- **Request Handler** – The requests sent to Solr are processed by these request handlers. The requests might be query requests or index update requests. Based on the requirements, the request handler must be selected. To pass a request to Solr, the handler is mapped to a certain URI end-point and the specified request is served by it.
- **Search Component** – A search component is a type (feature) of search provided in Apache Solr. It might be spell checking, query, faceting, hit highlighting, etc. These search components are registered as **search handlers**.
- **Query Parser** – The Apache Solr query parser parses queries that are then passed to Solr and checks them for syntactical errors. Upon completion of parsing, it translates them to a format that Lucene can "understand".
- **Response Writer** – A response writer is the component that generates the formatted output for user queries. Solr supports response formats such as XML, JSON, CSV, etc. Different response writers are available for each type of response.
- **Analyser/tokeniser** – Lucene recognises data as tokens. Solr analyses the content, splits it into tokens, and passes these tokens to Lucene. An analyser examines the text of fields and generates a token stream. The tokeniser breaks the token stream, prepared by the analyser, into tokens.
- **Update Request Processor** – Whenever an update request is sent to Solr, the request is executed via a set of plugins (nsmely, signature, logging, indexing) known as **update request processor**. This processor is responsible for modifications such as dropping a field, adding a field, etc.

⁵³ https://www.tutorialspoint.com/apache_solr/apache_solr_architecture.htm

Figure 12: Basic architecture of Solr

A search engine alternative, similar to Solr, is **Elasticsearch**⁵⁴. Elasticsearch is also built on top of the Apache Lucene library⁵⁵. It provides a distributed, multitenant-capable, full-text search engine. It is developed in Java, has an HTTP web interface, and makes use of schema-free JSON documents. Since both search technologies are based on similar principles, providing good scalability and performance, there is no question of selecting the best one of two. The final decisions will be made in the phase of development, when the HIKR and prototype e-KRP will be built.

4.3.4 EURAKNOS e-KRP architecture design and challenges

Given that the present report focusses on design issues related to the HIKR (to be implemented by the EURAKNOS repository), proceeding to details about the architecture of the e-KRP is beyond its scope. As mentioned above, all the architecture design-related issues will be presented in the Deliverable 4.3 report (“e-KRP documentation and guide”). However, there are a few points that will need to be taken into consideration for the next steps. First of all, the PostgreSQL database and Solr index/search system are part of the DSpace’s framework. This is not however the case, with Elasticsearch and the OpenLink Virtuoso triple store. Therefore, in order to make use of OpenVirtuoso instead of Fuseki⁵⁶, which is the default triplestore in DSpace, Fuseki will need to be circumvented. Such an effort may entail difficulties that will need to be considered and assessed in regard to the feasibility of this endeavor. The rationale for attempting to use OpenLink Virtuoso, instead of Fuseki, is that the former is a triple store solution widely adopted and used in European Research and Innovation projects. Technical issues may be also encountered in case of finally considering to use Elasticsearch for content indexing and search (instead of Solr). However, both Solr and Elasticsearch are products developed as part of the same project. Any technical difficulties that may be encountered in the process of developing the e-KRP will be reported in Deliverable 4.3 (“e-KRP documentation and guide”). Such a documentation will help to justify the final solutions that will be made in terms of the e-KRP system’s components and development.

⁵⁴ <https://www.elastic.co/elasticsearch/>

⁵⁵ <https://www.oreilly.com/library/view/elasticsearch-the-definitive/9781449358532/>

⁵⁶ <https://jena.apache.org/documentation/fuseki2/>

5. From HIKR to e-KRP (Digital Platform)

5.1 Types of knowledge reservoirs in current TNs

If we recap the classifications of Knowledge Reservoirs (KR) in current Thematic Networks (see D2.2), we identified 4 main types + 1 'hybrid' category:

1. KRs as a catalogue, choose your innovation
2. KRs as a library: find the knowledge on the right shelves
3. KRs as a practical digital guide book
4. KRs as a market place to exchange good practices
5. KRs as a mix of different categories

The main functionalities of these types of KRs are:

1. KRs as a catalogue, choose your innovation
 - This type of KR supports the user in his choices oriented in the search for practical solutions. So, these KRs reference innovative technical solutions. The key steps for consulting content are in the first place through the use of a search engine; in the second place search criteria are defined to filter solutions.
2. KRs as a library: find the knowledge on the right shelves
 - The main functionalities identified are a classification of contents by theme or type of content. The key steps for consulting content area guidance on the site according to a proposed thematic classification
3. KRs as a practical digital guide book
 - The main functionalities identified are a presentation of tricks and tips and very practical solutions. The key steps for consulting content are first, through the use of a search engine, second search criteria defined to filter solutions or defined on the subject on which it is focused.
4. KRs as a market place to exchange good practices
 - The main functionalities identified are a KR which does not host any knowledge content but which lists references accessible through URL links.

5.2 A (preliminary) future vision for the e-KRP in HIKR

When we take these different types of Knowledge Reservoirs into consideration and the user requirements (see D2.5), we foresee an evolutionary path for a future digital platform (e-KRP).

Based on the recommendations in D2.2 & The KIP meeting in Budapest (D2.5), The e-KRP should cater (at least) to these objectives:

- A central database that can store data from multiple Thematic Networks (main aim of the
- A user interface that enables searching this data in an intuitive way
- A personalized 'user journey' for the visitor, in which content is tailored to the actual visitor.
- Include functionalities to gather insights on user needs & content feedback
- Include functionalities that enable improvements over time (eg. statistics)
- Availability of different languages

In the context of Euraknos we are building a prototype of the e-KRP. This prototype should pave the way for the full-fledged platform 'FarmBook' (workname) in the future. To enable the continuous development of the future vision for the e-KRP, we suggest to focus first on the key functionality - a central database - and expand the scope of the platform in the coming years.

5.2.1 Phase 1: Prototype - LIBRARY

In phase 1 of the e-KRP: data from different thematic networks is stored in a central database and is easily searchable.

The main user journey is focused on easily searching relevant content in the database. The aim is a highly structured – functional – format for the platform with a clean and attractive appearance.

To cater to the philosophy of open access & the FAIR principles, the database will not require the user to create an account and login to the platform to search the database. All data is thus findable & accessible for the user.

The main disadvantage and direct consequence of an 'unregistered user' is that the level of personalization is limited. The visitor has to accept cookies in order to be able to allow any personalisation to be saved (2/3 of the cookies are automatically rejected by most web browsers). If the visitor deletes the cookies, the preferences and personalisation will be deleted as well. The visitor will however still be able to get suggestions for interesting content based on related tags (by contributors) and most viewed content within specific categories.

When we add a login module, the e-KRP allows visitors to register an account. The main advantage for the user in this state is that it allows the e-KRP to remember the user's preferences across sessions, and thus provide a more (automatically) tailored user journey.

The prototype will enable:

1. A central database for the data objects of at least 8 Thematic Networks
2. Direct access to content in the database (no login required)
3. Include a dashboard with a clean, attractive look
4. Searchable via filters (which can be combined)
 - New/old content
 - Most viewed
 - Theme (e.g.. precision farming, forestry,...)
 - Type of format (e.g.. video, audio, pdf,...)
 - Type of content (e.g.. practice abstract, fact sheet,...)
 - ...
5. 'Consume' content on the platform
 - Read articles, watch video, listen to audio,...
6. Download content from the platform
 - Download pdfs,...

5.2.2 Phase 2: Minimum Viable Product (MVP) – Platform

In phase 2 of the e-KRP (out of scope for the EURAKNOS project), the platform will build upon the central database and add new functionalities that cater to an expanded set of user needs.

The platform will enable:

1. Personalization after login
 - (eg. create an account, communicate & save preferences,...)
2. To gather basic insights on user needs & feedback on content
 - (eg. Usage statistics, general rating of content, express whether content was useful/relevant for me or not,...)
3. Recommendations for the end-user
 - (eg. Recommended content based on your search queries / preferences, people also looked for,...)
4. Alerts on relevant content
 - (eg. End users can set specific alerts for new content on a topic,...)
5. Understanding the ‘source’ of the content
 - (eg. Include the name of the contributing organization or ‘author’ of content,...)
6. Searching for contacts
 - (eg. Search organizations in my region, get contact details from authors or contributors,...)
7. ‘Basic’ sharing options of content to social platforms
 - (eg. Share to Facebook, LinkedIn,...)
8. Include features for accessibility
 - (eg. Increased contrast and font legibility,...)

5.2.3 Phase 3: Farmbook

In the third evolution of the platform, the database will still be the foundation, but the purpose of Farmbook will broaden to workspace & social platform.

In this phase the platform caters to user needs, such as:

1. Features that enable an interactive onboarding flow for new users on how to use the platform
 - (eg. A step-by-step guide, asking for interests,...)
2. Extensive functionalities that allow the end-user to provide feedback on specific content pieces

D3.2 – Report on HIKR design

- (eg. Comments section, suggest edits,...)
- 3. A contributor community, with specific guidelines for contribution and curation
 - (eg. Process, do's & don'ts,...)
- 4. Workspace functionalities for end-users
 - (eg. Keeping notes, adding 'own' links to other resources,...)
- 5. Automated newsletter functionalities, that collects & combines relevant new content
 - (eg. Recommendations for you based on your search queries,...)
- 6. Communities of end-users that can connect on specific themes, topics or events
 - (eg. Share experience with other farmers, links to farmers who have used the solution, suggestions of 'friends',...)

5.2.4 Future

Stepping into the future, Farmbook could evolve towards a suite of modules & features that could enable thematic networks – and any type of multi-actor project – in their working.

A broader set of features could include:

1. A CMS (Content Management System) with website templates dedicated to the needs of multi-actor projects (*cfr. Squarespace, Wordpress,...*)
2. Built-in features for communication & dissemination
 - A design toolkit with visual identity components
 - Newsletter builder with templates (*cfr. Mailchimp,...*)
3. Built-in features for thematic networks to interact with their target audience and gauge for content needs
 - Learning Spaces & Webinar functionalities
 - Communities organized & managed by Thematic Networks

5.3 General usability and accessibility guidelines for the e-KRP

In the previous sections we have demonstrated that the creation of the database model for a HIKR benefits from having knowledge about the information needs of an end user in order to create a suitable ontology which allows the end user to find information using categories that fit the mental model of the end user when searching for information about the relevant topic. When bringing information from the back-end of the HIKR (i.e. the database) to the front-end (the digital platform with which the end user will interact), general knowledge about how an end user typically interacts with digital environments needs to be taken into account in order to create an environment that end users will use and keep on using.

Over the last two decades there has been a gradual change from perceiving digital products as mere information providers to digital products as more personalised experience providers which take into account the needs of relevant end users. Additionally, an EU directive (2016/2102) aimed at providing

better access to digital products of public services for people with diverse abilities is currently shaping the way digital products are being developed by forcing digital designers to take into account the point of view of different end users. In this section we'll provide an overview of guidelines to take into account when designing digital products to comply with usability and accessibility standards expected by end users.

5.3.1 Recommendations on usability & accessibility

We have collected the state-of-the art in usability & accessibility guidelines. These can be found in ANNEX 3.

Information presentation

The platform and its interface should consistently provide information in terminology that is understood and expected by as many relevant end users as possible.

The provided information needs to be concise and to the point as we want to prevent that end users are overwhelmed and dissuaded from using the platform due to an overload of information.

The most important information needs to be presented first and clearly marked so end users notice it first and can decide whether the information is relevant to their search.

The information flow

End users need to be provided with appropriate information as to where they are on the platform and how they can get back to a reference point such as the homepage.

A central navigation needs to be accessible on each page of the platform to allow end users to navigate through the platform at all times.

The central navigation should offer a limited amount (between 4 and 6) of clearly defined categories to choose from in order to prevent end users from doubting which category they need to choose to attain the correct information.

A search bar should be easily accessible to accommodate end users who choose to perform a specific search query.

Visual design

The information needs to be presented in an attractive way in line with contemporary standards of attractive visual design. The visual design cannot be outdated and needs to fit the expectations of the end users as this could give end users the impression that the presented information is outdated as well.

6. Conclusions & Next Steps

In task 3.2, we have:

- Developed and validated a data model which seems to be future-proof. This data model will serve as the basis for the EURAKNOS platform (e-KRP) and will be presented as a guideline to current & future Thematic Networks.
- Decided on a technology stack that is in line with multiple other projects that are either initiated or funded by the European Commission. This to ensure maximum interoperability with other & future projects, and to allow other teams to continue to work on the efforts in the EURAKNOS project
- Suggested a potential phasing of features for the EURAKNOS platform, beyond the scope of the EURAKNOS project.
- Researched the state-of-the-art in usability & accessibility guidelines to enable a better design of the user experience & user interface. This will ultimately ensure a better adoption of the platform by the end-users: farmers, foresters & advisors.

The outputs of D3.2 will feed into the technical guidelines for a High-Impact Knowledge Reservoir (HIKR) (D3.6), and into WP4 for the development of the prototype of the EURAKNOS Platform.

7. Annex 1: Datatype properties of the EURAKNOS data model's classes

Tables 12 to 26 below provide the names and short descriptions of the datatype properties, identified and defined for each class of the data model, together with the (types of) values they can receive.

Table 12: Datatype properties of the *ThematicNetwork* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
acronym	The acronym of the Thematic Network.	String
fullName	The full name of the Thematic Network.	String
url	URL of the Thematic Network's website.	String
description	Textual description of what the Thematic Network is about.	String

Table 13: Datatype properties of the *Domain* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
name	The name of the Thematic Network's domain.	{Crop farming, Animal husbandry and welfare, Forestry}
description	Textual description of the Thematic Network's domain.	String

Table 14: Datatype properties of the *Topic* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
name	The name of the topic addressed by a specific output of a Thematic Network.	Crop farming practices, actors, systems, types of crops, infrastructures, tools, technologies, climatic zones, environment, socio-economic context
		Animal husbandry and welfare practices, actors, systems, types of animals, infrastructures, tools, technologies, climatic zones, environment, socio-economic context
		Forestry practices, actors, systems, types of forests, infrastructures, tools, technologies, climatic zones, environment, socio-economic context
description	Textual description of the output's topic.	String

Table 15: Datatype properties of the *Output* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
title	The title of an output of a Thematic Network	String
description	Textual description of what an output is about.	String
contentInLanguage	The language(s) in which the content of an output is available.	{Bulgarian, Croatian, Czech, Danish, Dutch, English, Estonian, Finnish, French, German, Greek, Hungarian, Irish, Italian, Latvian, Lithuanian, Maltese, Polish, Portuguese, Romanian, Slovak, Slovene, Spanish, Swedish}

Datatype property	Description	Values
keywords	A list of keywords that are associated with an output of the Thematic Network.	String
fileUrl	URL to the “source” of the output (where applicable).	String
dateCreated	The date on which an output was created (full date or year).	String
license	A description of specific licensing terms (e.g. a Creative Commons license) that describe how an output may be further exploited.	String
geographicLocation	The geographic location (country/-ies) to which the content of an output (for instance, solution to a problem or innovative practice) relates.	{Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg, Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden, Switzerland, United Kingdom}
purpose	The reason/purpose for which an output has been produced.	{access to data, communication, dissemination, education/training}
fileSize	The size of the file (in KBs/MBs) through which an output of a Thematic Network is available.	String

Table 16: Datatype properties of the *EndUserType* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
name	The name of an end-user type that is going to use an output of a Thematic Network.	{advisor, bee keeper, consumer, distributor, entrepreneur, farmer, fisherman, forester, instructor, livestock breeder, policy maker, researcher, student, trader, educator/trainer, university professor}
description	Description of an end-user type that is going to use an output of a Thematic Network.	String

Table 17: Datatype properties of the *Creator* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
name	The name of an output creator.	String
description	Textual description of an output creator.	String

The Audio, Dataset, Document, Image, Presentation, Software and Video classes are subclasses of the Output class, which means that all the properties of the Output class are inherited by its subclasses. Yet, the subclasses of the Output class have also a number of additional properties. These additional properties relate to the **type** and **format**. These two datatype properties are defined in response to the model-related requirement having to do with the need to: (i) identify and define

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the types of the data objects available per category/kind; and (ii) to capture the the variety of formats in which the data objects become available.

Table 18: Additional datatype properties of the Audio class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of an audio object (available value options adhere to open file formats).	{.m4a, .caf, .flac, .mpc, .mp+, .mpp, .mp3, .bit, .ogg, .ogv, .oga, .ogx, .ogm, .spx, .opus, .spx, .wv}
type	The type of an audio object.	{educational/training podcast, event capturing podcast, interview, solo podcast, tutorial, guide, commentary, panel discussion, question-and-answer podcast, on-demand seminar, audio magazine, other}

Table 19: Additional datatype properties of the Dataset class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of a dataset.	String
type	The type of a dataset.	{auditory data, crop-related data, geospatial data, graph-related data, imagery data, input-related data, network-related data, temporal data, textual data, video data, yield-related data, other}

Table 20: Additional datatype properties of the Document class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of a document (available value options adhere to open file formats).	{.txt, .csv, .htm/.html, markdown, .dvi, .dbk, .xml, .epub, .fb2, .fbz, .docx, .docm, .doc, .odt, .fodt, .oxps, .xps, .pdf, .ps, .xls, .xlsx, .xhtml, .xht}
type	The type of a document.	{article in conference proceedings, book, booklet, brochure/flyer, chapter in edited volume, deliverable report, factsheet, handbook, guide, journal article, manual, milestone report, newsletter, practice abstract, press release, spreadsheet, review document, report/paper, technical article, technical information/ specifications card, tutorial, other}

Table 21: Additional datatype properties of the Image class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of the image object (available value options adhere to open file formats).	{.png, .apng, .flif, .gbr, .gif, .jp2, .j2k, .jpf, .jpx, .jpm, .mj2, .mng, .exr, .pdf, .png, .svg, .svgz, .webp, .xpm}
type	The type of the image object.	{chart/graph, static figure/image, interactive figure/image, infographic, static map, interactive map, other}

Table 22: Additional datatype properties of the Presentation class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of a presentation (available value	{.pdf, .potm, .potx, .ppt, .pptx}

	options adhere to open file formats).	
type	The type of a presentation.	{educational/training presentation, guide, informative presentation, tutorial, motivational presentation, decision-making presentation, problem-solving presentation, other}

Table 23: Additional datatype properties of the *Software* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of a software application.	{.exe, .app, .vb, .scr}
type	The type of a software application.	{AI software, business software, data repository/database, data analysis software, decision support tool, educational/training software, FMIS, game, scientific software, simulation, other}

Table 24: Additional datatype properties of the *Video* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
format	The file format of a video (available value options adhere to open file formats)..	{.drc, .mkv, .mk3d, .mka, .mks, .mp4, .m4a, .m4p, .m4b, .m4r, .m4v, .webm, .ogv, .ogg}
type	The type of a video object.	{vlog, webinar, guide, event capturing video, tutorial/how-to video, presentation/live talk capturing video, interview video, product/feature review video, documentary video, testimonial, question-and-answer video, case study, simulation video, educational/training video, event capturing video, other}

The *Individual* and *Organisation* classes are subclasses of the *Creator* class. This means that all the properties of the *Creator* class are inherited by its subclasses. However, the two subclasses of the *Creator* class have an property as well. This additional property relates to the **type** of the *Individual* or *Organisation* and has been defined in response to the requirement having to do with the consideration of entities, relations, and entity properties that will allow to capture and provide provenance information.

Table 25: Additional datatype properties of the *Individual* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
type	The type of an individual.	{adviser, bee keeper, consumer, distributor, entrepreneur, farmer, fisherman, forester, instructor, livestock breeder, policy maker, researcher, student, trader, educator/trainer, university professor, other}

Table 26: Additional datatype properties of the *Organisation* class, description, and potential (types) values

Datatype property	Description	Values
involvement	Type of involvement an organization has in the Thematic Network.	{leading organization, participating organization}

type	The type of an organisation.	{advisors’ association, AKIS community, consulting company, consumers’ association, distribution company, environmental organisation, farmers’ association, food industry, input industry, NGO, public authority, retailer, research institute, school, SME, technical institute, trading company, training organization, university, other}
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8. The EURAKNOS data model in RDF/XML syntax

```

<?xml version="1.0"?>
<rdf:RDF
xmlns="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1
#"
xml:base="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model
_v1"
xmlns:owl="http://www.w3.org/2002/07/owl#"
xmlns:rdf="http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#"
xmlns:xml="http://www.w3.org/XML/1998/namespace"
xmlns:xsd="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#"
xmlns:rdfs="http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#"
xmlns:schema="https://schema.org/">
  <owl:Ontology
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model
_v1">
    <rdfs:comment>This is version 1.0 of the EURAKNOS data model. It is published and made
available under the Creative Commons &quot;Attribution 4.0 International (CC BY 4.0)&quot; license
(https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>EURAKNOS data model</rdfs:label>
    <owl:versionInfo>version 1.0</owl:versionInfo>
    <schema:license>https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/</schema:license>
  </owl:Ontology>

  <!--
  ////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
  //
  // Annotation properties
  //
  ////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
  -->

  <!-- https://schema.org/license -->
  <owl:AnnotationProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/license"/>

  <!--
  ////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
  
```



```

//
// Object Properties
//
////////////////////////////////////
-->

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#affiliatedWith -->
  <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#affiliatedWith">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/Person"/>
  <rdfs:domain>
  <owl:Restriction>
  <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#affiliatedWith"/>
  <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
  <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/Person"/>
  </owl:Restriction>
  </rdfs:domain>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Organization"/>
  <rdfs:range>
  <owl:Restriction>
  <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#affiliatedWith"/>
  <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
  <owl:onClass rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Organization"/>
  </owl:Restriction>
  </rdfs:range>
  <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that an individual (probably involved in the creation of a Thematic Network's output) is affiliated with one or more organisations.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>affiliatedWith</rdfs:label>
  </owl:ObjectProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#associatedWith -->

```



```

    <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#associatedWith">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>
    <rdfs:domain>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#associatedWith"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:domain>
    <rdfs:range
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>
    <rdfs:range>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#associatedWith"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:range>
    <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that the topic of a Thematic Network's output is associated with a Domain (i.e., an agricultural sector).</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>associatedWith</rdfs:label>
    </owl:ObjectProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#coordinatedBy -->
    <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#coordinatedBy">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    <rdfs:domain>

```



```

    <owl:Restriction>
      <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#coordinatedBy"/>
        <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">0</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
      <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
  </rdfs:domain>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Organization"/>
  <rdfs:range>
    <owl:Restriction>
      <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#coordinatedBy"/>
        <owl:qualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:qualifiedCardinality>
      <owl:onClass rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Organization"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
  </rdfs:range>
  <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that a Thematic Network has a coordinating organisation.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>coordinatedBy</rdfs:label>
</owl:ObjectProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#createdBy -->
  <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#createdBy">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:domain>
      <owl:Restriction>
        <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#createdBy"/>
          <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
        <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>

```



```

    </owl:Restriction>
  </rdfs:domain>
  <rdfs:range
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator"/>
  <rdfs:range>
    <owl:Restriction>
      <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#createdBy"/>
        <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
        <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator"/>
          </owl:Restriction>
        </rdfs:range>
        <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that an output of a Thematic Network has one or more creators.</rdfs:comment>
        <rdfs:label>createdBy</rdfs:label>
      </owl:ObjectProperty>

  <!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#hasTopic -->
  <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#hasTopic">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:domain>
      <owl:Restriction>
        <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#hasTopic"/>
          <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
          <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
            </owl:Restriction>
        </rdfs:domain>
        <rdfs:range
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>
          <rdfs:range>
            <owl:Restriction>

```



```

    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#hasTopic"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:range>
    <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that an output of a Thematic Network may have one or more topics.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>hasTopic</rdfs:label>
    </owl:ObjectProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#relatesTo -->
    <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#relatesTo">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    <rdfs:domain>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#relatesTo"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">0</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:domain>
    <rdfs:range
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>
    <rdfs:range>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#relatesTo"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>

```



```

    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:range>
    <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that a Thematic Network relates to a Domain
(i.e., an agricultural sector).</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>relatesTo</rdfs:label>
    </owl:ObjectProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#usedBy
-->
    <owl:ObjectProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#usedBy">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:domain>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#usedBy"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:domain>
    <rdfs:range
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#EndUserType"/>
    <rdfs:range>
    <owl:Restriction>
    <owl:onProperty
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#usedBy"/>
    <owl:minQualifiedCardinality
rdf:datatype="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#nonNegativeInteger">1</owl:minQualifiedCardinality>
    <owl:onClass
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#EndUserType"/>
    </owl:Restriction>
    </rdfs:range>
    <rdfs:comment>Object property used to denote that an output of a Thematic Network is intended
to be used by one or more types of end-users.</rdfs:comment>

```



```

    <rdfs:label>usedBy</rdfs:label>
  </owl:ObjectProperty>

  <!--
  ////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
  //
  // Data properties
  //
  ////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////////
  -->

  <!--
  http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#format
  -->
    <owl:DatatypeProperty
  rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model
  _v1#format">
      <rdfs:domain
  rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
  del_v1#https://schema.org/PresentationDigitalDocument"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/AudioObject"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Dataset"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/ImageObject"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/TextDigitalDocument"/>
        <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/VideoObject"/>
        <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
        <rdfs:comment>The file format of the Thematic Network's output (e.g.,
  &quot;pdf&quot;).</rdfs:comment>
        <rdfs:label>format</rdfs:label>
      </owl:DatatypeProperty>

  <!--
  http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#title -->
    <owl:DatatypeProperty
  rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model
  _v1#title">
      <rdfs:domain
  rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
  del_v1#Output"/>
        <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
        <rdfs:comment>The title of an output of a Thematic Network.</rdfs:comment>
        <rdfs:label>title</rdfs:label>
      </owl:DatatypeProperty>

  <!--
  http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#type --
  >

```



```

    <owl:DatatypeProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#type">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/Person"/>
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/PresentationDigitalDocument"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/AudioObject"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Dataset"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/ImageObject"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/Organization"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/TextDigitalDocument"/>
    <rdfs:domain rdf:resource="https://schema.org/VideoObject"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>The type of the Thematic Network's output. There are different types per output category.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>type</rdfs:label>
    </owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/name -->
    <owl:DatatypeProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/name">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>The full name of the Thematic Network.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>fullName</rdfs:label>
    </owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/url -->
    <owl:DatatypeProperty
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/url">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#anyURI"/>
    <rdfs:comment>The URL to the web location from where the Thematic Network's output has been retrieved.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>fileUrl</rdfs:label>
    </owl:DatatypeProperty>

```



```

<!-- https://schema.org/alternateName -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/alternateName">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The acronym of the Thematic Network.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>acronym</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

```

```

<!-- https://schema.org/contentLocation -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/contentLocation">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The location depicted or described in the content of the Thematic
Network's output.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>geographicLocation</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

```

```

<!-- https://schema.org/dateCreated -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/dateCreated">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The date on which the output of a Thematic Nertwork was
created.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:comment>dateCreated</rdfs:comment>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

```

```

<!-- https://schema.org/description -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/description">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Creator"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Domain"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#EndUserType"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>

```



```

    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Topic"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A description of an item/instance.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>description</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/fileSize -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/fileSize">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>Size of the file (e.g., 18MB). In the absence of a unit (MB, KB etc.), KB will be
assumed.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>fileSize</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/inLanguage -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/inLanguage">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>The language of the content of the Thematic Network's
output.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>contentInLanguage</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/keywords -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/keywords">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
    <rdfs:comment>Keywords used to describe the content of a Thematic Network's output.
Multiple entries in a keywords list are typically delimited by commas.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>keywords</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/license -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/license">
    <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#anyURI"/>

```



```

</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/name -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/name">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#EndUserType"/>
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The name of an item/instance.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>name</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/potentialAction -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/potentialAction">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The purpose for which the output of the Thematic Network has been created.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>purpose</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!-- https://schema.org/url -->
<owl:DatatypeProperty rdf:about="https://schema.org/url">
  <rdfs:domain
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>
  <rdfs:range rdf:resource="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#anyURI"/>
  <rdfs:comment>The URL to the Thematic Network's official website.</rdfs:comment>
  <rdfs:label>url</rdfs:label>
</owl:DatatypeProperty>

<!--
////////////////////////////////////
//
// Classes
//
////////////////////////////////////
-->

```



```

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Domain"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#EndUserType -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#EndUserType"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#ThematicNetwork"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Topic"/>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/Person -->
  <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/Person">

```



```

    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Creator"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A person (alive, dead, undead, or fictional).</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Individual</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!--
http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://
/schema.org/PresentationDigitalDocument -->
    <owl:Class
rdf:about="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#https://schema.org/PresentationDigitalDocument">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A file containing slides or used for a presentation.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Presentation</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/AudioObject -->
    <owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/AudioObject">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>An audio file.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Audio</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/Dataset -->
    <owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/Dataset">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A body of structured information describing some topic(s) of
interest.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Dataset</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/ImageObject -->
    <owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/ImageObject">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_model_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>An image file.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Image</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/Organization -->
    <owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/Organization">

```



```

    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Creator"/>
    <rdfs:comment>An organization such as a school, NGO, corporation, club, etc.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:comment>Organisation</rdfs:comment>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication -->
<owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/SoftwareApplication">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A software application.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Software</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/TextDigitalDocument -->
<owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/TextDigitalDocument">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A file composed primarily of text.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Document</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!-- https://schema.org/VideoObject -->
<owl:Class rdf:about="https://schema.org/VideoObject">
    <rdfs:subClassOf
rdf:resource="http://www.semanticweb.org/hercules_pan/ontologies/2021/8/EURAKNOS_data_mo
del_v1#Output"/>
    <rdfs:comment>A video file.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>Video</rdfs:label>
</owl:Class>

<!--
////////////////////////////////////
//
// Annotations
//
////////////////////////////////////
-->

<rdf:Description rdf:about="https://schema.org/license">
    <rdfs:comment>license document that applies to the content of the Thematic Network's
output. It is typically indicated by an URL.</rdfs:comment>
    <rdfs:label>license</rdfs:label>
</rdf:Description>
</rdf:RDF>

```


<!-- Generated by the OWL API (version 4.5.9.2019-02-01T07:24:44Z)
<https://github.com/owlcs/owlapi> -->

9. Annex 3: Details about the advisor survey conducted in the context of the EUFRAS meeting in Athens

The survey results presented in the “**Considerations for selecting data objects to store into the High Impact Knowledge Reservoir**” section have been obtained from an advisor survey that took place in the context of the EUFRAS meeting in Athens (24 - 25 February, 2020). The survey questionnaire that was used for the needs of the survey was designed by PSKW and comprised a total number of 12 items. The full list of questionnaire items is provided below. The sample of survey participants consisted had a size of 32 ($n = 32$). As made evident from the graphs presented in Figures 12 to 14 below, there was an equal representation of females and males in the sample (female advisors = 43.8%; male advisors = 50.0%).

Figure 13: Gender distribution in the sample of advisors that participated in the EUFRAS meeting survey

The majority of sample subjects belong to the 40-50 and the 50-60 age groups with the frequencies of these age groups being 29.0% and 25.8% respectively. The frequency of subjects in the age range between 30 and 40 years old was 16.1%, whereas 12.9% of the sample subjects have an age between 20 and 30 years old. The age group that was least represented in the sample was that from 60 to 70 years old, which accounted for 9.7% of the sample size.

Figure 14: Distribution of ages in the sample of advisors that participated in the EUFRAS meeting survey

As far as nationalities are concerned, the majority of survey participants come from Greece (15.6%), 12.5% are Bulgarian, 9.4 % are German, and then we have Latvian, Estonian, Spanish participants, as well as participants from Switzerland (6.3%). The rest of the nationalities were represented at a rate of 3.1%.

Figure 15: Nationalities of survey participants

Q1: There are new project results available. How would you like to be informed about this?
(multiple choice)

1. Technical magazines
2. Websites of research stations
3. Newsletters
4. Meetings, Study days
5. Facebook
6. WhatsApp
7. Twitter
8. LinkedIn
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q2: Where do you search for the information you need? (multiple choice)

1. Technical magazines
2. Websites of research stations
3. Search engines
4. Scientific databases
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q3: In what language do you search for information? (multiple choice)

1. English
2. Native language
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q4: What kind of content/information would you prefer? (multiple choice)

1. Presentation of best practices
2. Presentation of innovative practices
3. Information material (just to know what is going on in the community)
4. Educational/training material
5. Guidelines
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q5: Would you opt for being provided content/information based on your profile and history of interactions? (single answer)

1. Yes
2. No
99. No answer

Q6: In what phase of a project would you like to be involved? (multiple choice)

1. Project ideas based on your own experiences
2. Project writing
3. Participation in steering group/user group
4. Expert panel following up tests
5. Testing technologies
6. Participation in workshops, study days, meetings
7. Feedback on project impact
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q7: What group do you belong to? (single answer)

1. Grower
2. Advisor

3. Researcher
4. Industry
5. Student
6. Teacher
7. Policy maker
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q8: What is your nationality? (single answer)

98. Specify:
99. No answer

Q9: Which age category do you belong to? (single answer)

1. <20
2. 20 – 30
3. 30 – 40
4. 40 – 50
5. 50 – 60
6. 60 – 70
7. >70
99. No answer

Q10: What gender are you? (single answer)

1. Female
2. Non-binary/fluid
3. Male
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q11: What kind of information would you like to be delivered as part of search results display? (multiple choice)

1. Title of the provided result item.
2. Short textual description of the provided result item.
3. List of keywords associated with the provided result item.
4. Descriptive icon of the provided result item.
5. Format of the provided result item (pdf, ppt, jpg, mp4, etc.)
6. Type of provided result item (factsheet, leaflet, report, video, podcast, scientific article etc.)
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

Q12: Which of the following kinds of digital content is most preferable to you? (multiple choice)

1. Audio
2. Image
3. Presentation (slideshow)
4. Text
5. Video
98. Other (Specify:)
99. No answer

10. Annex 4: State-of-the Art in Usability & Accessibility Guidelines

10.1 Usability guidelines

User experience design (UX-design) attempts to make the use of (digital) products as user friendly as is possible. In general, good UX-design will not be noticed by the user, while bad UX-design will. At a more abstract level UX-design tends to follow a set of guidelines which the designer tries to respect when designing a digital product. As digital technology can change rapidly, the implementation of these guidelines will differ depending on the available technology but also on trends set by dominant digital product providers (e.g. Apple, Facebook, Google). Instead of advising designers to use, for instance, a specific button and location to share content, designers are advised to detect and follow the current trend in order to make the experience over different digital products as seamless as possible. This also implies that a sustainable digital product is one which is updated regularly to match the usability trends prominent at that moment. Listed below are several best-practice lists of guidelines which show overlap, but help UX-designers create user friendly digital products.

1) TEN USABILITY HEURISTICS FOR INTERFACE DESIGN

In 1990 Jakob Nielsen and Rolf Molich⁵⁷ created a list of usability heuristics for user interface design which are still considered relevant and have been further refined through studies.

1. Visibility of system status

The system should always keep users informed about what is going on, through appropriate feedback within reasonable time.

2. Match between system and the real world

The system should speak the users' language, with words, phrases and concepts familiar to the user, rather than system-oriented terms. Follow real-world conventions, making information appear in a natural and logical order.

3. User control and freedom

Users often choose system functions by mistake and will need a clearly marked "emergency exit" to leave the unwanted state without having to go through an extended dialogue. Support undo and redo.

4. Consistency and standards

Users should not have to wonder whether different words, situations, or actions mean the same thing.

5. Error prevention

Even better than good error messages is a careful design which prevents a problem from occurring in the first place. Either eliminate error-prone conditions or check for them and present users with a confirmation option before they commit to the action.

6. Recognition rather than recall

⁵⁷ <https://www.nngroup.com/articles/ten-usability-heuristics/>

D3.2 – Report on HIKR design

Minimize the user's memory load by making objects, actions, and options visible. The user should not have to remember information from one part of the dialogue to another. Instructions for use of the system should be visible or easily retrievable whenever appropriate.

7. Flexibility and efficiency of use

Accelerators — unseen by the novice user — may often speed up the interaction for the expert user such that the system can cater to both inexperienced and experienced users. Allow users to tailor frequent actions.

8. Aesthetic and minimalist design

Dialogues should not contain information which is irrelevant or rarely needed. Every extra unit of information in a dialogue competes with the relevant units of information and diminishes their relative visibility.

9. Help users recognize, diagnose, and recover from errors

Error messages should be expressed in plain language (no codes), precisely indicate the problem, and constructively suggest a solution.

10. Help and documentation

Even though it is better if the system can be used without documentation, it may be necessary to provide help and documentation. Any such information should be easy to search, focused on the user's task, list concrete steps to be carried out, and not be too large.

2) TEN PRINCIPLES FOR GOOD DESIGN

In the 1960 Dieter Rams⁵⁸ defined Ten principles for good design which apply to design in general but have found their way to the minds of many digital designers.

1. Good design is innovative

The possibilities for innovation are not, by any means, exhausted. Technological development is always offering new opportunities for innovative design. But innovative design always develops in tandem with innovative technology, and can never be an end in itself.

2. Good design makes a product useful

A product is bought to be used. It has to satisfy certain criteria, not only functional, but also psychological and aesthetic. Good design emphasises the usefulness of a product whilst disregarding anything that could possibly detract from it.

3. Good design is aesthetic

The aesthetic quality of a product is integral to its usefulness because products we use every day affect our person and our well-being. But only well-executed objects can be beautiful.

4. Good design makes a product understandable

It clarifies the products structure. Better still, it can make the product talk. At best, it is self-explanatory.

5. Good design is unobtrusive

⁵⁸ <https://www.designprinciplesftw.com/collections/ten-principles-for-good-design>

D3.2 – Report on HIKR design

Products fulfilling a purpose are like tools. They are neither decorative objects nor works of art. Their design should therefore be both neutral and restrained, to leave room for the users self-expression.

6. Good design is honest

It does not make a product more innovative, powerful or valuable than it really is. It does not attempt to manipulate the consumer with promises that cannot be kept.

7. Good design is long-lasting

It avoids being fashionable and therefore never appears antiquated. Unlike fashionable design, it lasts many years - even in today's throwaway society.

8. Good design is thorough down to the last detail

Nothing must be arbitrary or left to chance. Care and accuracy in the design process show respect towards the consumer.

9. Good design is environmentally friendly

Design makes an important contribution to the preservation of the environment. It conserves resources and minimises physical and visual pollution throughout the lifecycle of the product.

10. Good design is as little design as possible

Less, but better - because it concentrates on the essential aspects, and the products are not burdened with non-essentials.

Back to purity, back to simplicity.

3) EIGHT GOLDEN RULES FOR INTERFACE DESIGN

In 1987 Ben Shneiderman⁵⁹ distilled Eight Golden Rules of Interface Design from the research he did in Human Computer Interaction.

1. Strive for consistency

Consistent sequences of actions should be required in similar situations; identical terminology should be used in prompts, menus, and help screens; and consistent colour, layout, capitalization, fonts, and so on, should be employed throughout. Exceptions, such as required confirmation of the delete command or no echoing of passwords, should be comprehensible and limited in number.

2. Seek universal usability

Recognize the needs of diverse users and design for plasticity, facilitating transformation of content. Novice to expert differences, age ranges, disabilities, international variations, and technological diversity each enrich the spectrum of requirements that guides design. Adding features for novices, such as explanations, and features for experts, such as shortcuts and faster pacing, enriches the interface design and improves perceived quality.

3. Offer informative feedback

For every user action, there should be an interface feedback. For frequent and minor actions, the response can be modest, whereas for infrequent and major actions, the response should be more substantial. Visual presentation of the objects of interest provides a convenient environment for showing changes explicitly (see the discussion of direct manipulation in Chapter 7).

⁵⁹ <https://www.cs.umd.edu/~ben/goldenrules.html>

4. Design dialogs to yield closure

Sequences of actions should be organized into groups with a beginning, middle, and end. Informative feedback at the completion of a group of actions gives users the satisfaction of accomplishment, a sense of relief, a signal to drop contingency plans from their minds, and an indicator to prepare for the next group of actions. For example, e-commerce websites move users from selecting products to the checkout, ending with a clear confirmation page that completes the transaction.

5. Prevent errors

As much as possible, design the interface so that users cannot make serious errors; for example, gray out menu items that are not appropriate and do not allow alphabetic characters in numeric entry fields (Section 3.3.5). If users make an error, the interface should offer simple, constructive, and specific instructions for recovery. For example, users should not have to retype an entire name-address form if they enter an invalid zip code but rather should be guided to repair only the faulty part. Erroneous actions should leave the interface state unchanged, or the interface should give instructions about restoring the state.

6. Permit easy reversal of actions

As much as possible, actions should be reversible. This feature relieves anxiety, since users know that errors can be undone, and encourages exploration of unfamiliar options. The units of reversibility may be a single action, a data-entry task, or a complete group of actions, such as entry of a name-address block.

7. Keep users in control

Experienced users strongly desire the sense that they are in charge of the interface and that the interface responds to their actions. They don't want surprises or changes in familiar behaviour, and they are annoyed by tedious data-entry sequences, difficulty in obtaining necessary information, and inability to produce their desired result.

8. Reduce short-term memory load

Humans' limited capacity for information processing in short-term memory (the rule of thumb is that people can remember "seven plus or minus two chunks" of information) requires that designers avoid interfaces in which users must remember information from one display and then use that information on another display. It means that cellphones should not require re-entry of phone numbers, website locations should remain visible, and lengthy forms should be compacted to fit a single display.

4) DESIGN PRINCIPLES FOR REDUCING COGNITIVE LOAD

More recently Jon Yablonski⁶⁰ introduced several design principles to reduce cognitive load which prove to be helpful as an overload of information from different sources is making it increasingly difficult for users to process information provided without taking these principles into account.

1. Avoid Unnecessary Elements

Like everything in design, less is more. Any element that isn't helping the user achieve their goal is working against them because they must process it and store it in working memory, alongside the

⁶⁰ <https://jonyablonski.com/articles/2015/design-principles-for-reducing-cognitive-load/>

things that will help them. Avoiding excessive colours, imagery, design flourishes, or layouts that don't add value is crucial. But simplicity comes with a caveat: don't overvalue it at the cost of clarity.

2. Leverage Common Design Patterns

By leveraging common design patterns when it makes sense, you are giving the user familiar elements which they already understand. This in turn reduces the amount of learning they need to do, thus enabling them to move right along and get closer to achieving their goal. My favourite sources for design pattern inspiration are Design Patterns on CodePen and the Blueprint Archives on Codrops.

3. Eliminate Unnecessary Tasks

Anywhere you are asking the user to read content, remember information or make a decision contributes to cognitive load. Whenever possible, it is good to shift these tasks away from the user and make it easier for them to stay focused on their goal. While it isn't possible to remove all tasks, there is usually an opportunity to offload some task by setting defaults that can be edited, or leveraging previously entered information. Some companies are even taking this a step further with anticipatory design.

4. Minimize Choices

As previously mentioned, our working memory is limited. When confronted with too many choices, cognitive load will increase due to decision paralysis. It is important that we minimize the choices the user must make at any given moment, especially in places such as navigation, forms, and drop-downs.

5. Display Choices as a Group

When choices are split into separate groups and hidden, users often mistake the options that are visible as the complete group. This means that users are likely to never find the additional choices, which not only limits what is available to them, but also makes it more difficult to decide on which option to select because they are not aware of the alternatives. Therefore, it is best to eliminate the resulting cognitive load by always displaying choices as a group.

6. Strive for Readability

Making our content legible isn't enough — we need to make it readable. This means our typography must be aesthetically pleasing, appropriate for the content and easy to read while design remains relatively invisible. By doing this, we can ensure there are as little distractions as possible for the user, which results in a better understanding of the content by the user.

7. Use Iconography with Caution

Research has shown that iconography can be hard to memorize and, contrary to intuition, can increase cognitive load by requiring mental processing to infer meaning or recognize. While universally understood icons work well (ie. print, close, play/pause, reply, tweet, share on Facebook), most are subject to the user's understanding based on previous experience (in which there is no standard). When leveraging the power of iconography, it is best to accompany them with text labels to communicate the meaning and reduce ambiguity.

10.1.1 Accessibility principles and guidelines

The European Commission and Council aim to create a more digitally inclusive environment and have create a directive for digital products of public services.

The EU directive 2016/2102⁶¹:

- covers websites and apps of public sector bodies, with a limited number of exceptions (e.g. broadcasters, live streaming);
- refers to specific standards to make websites and mobile apps more accessible. Such standards require for instance that there should be a text description for images, or that users are able to interact with a website without using a mouse, which can be difficult for some people with disabilities;
- requires the publication of an accessibility statement for each website and mobile app, describing the level of accessibility and indicating any content that is not accessible;
- calls for a feedback mechanism which the users can use to flag accessibility problems or to ask for the information contained in a non-accessible content;
- expects regular monitoring of public sector websites and apps by Member States, and that they report on the results of the monitoring. These reports have to be communicated to the Commission and to be made public for the first time by 23 December 2021.

The World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)⁶², involved in developing Web standards, has created a set of accessibility standards and guidelines which aid digital designers and developers to create accessible digital products.

Examples include:

- Providing text alternatives for non-text content such as images (through descriptions) and video or audio files (through transcripts)
- Allowing navigation through a digital product without having to rely on a mouse (easy navigation through keyboard)
- Users can easily navigate, find content, and determine where they are
- Content appears and operates in predictable ways by providing a easily identifiable navigation and using consistency in the labelling of the navigation categories
- Content is compatible with current and future user tools by providing a name, role, and value for non-standard user interface components

⁶¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2016/2102/oj>

⁶² <https://www.w3.org/standards/webdesign/accessibility>,
<https://www.w3.org/WAI/fundamentals/accessibility-principles/>

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